

Report on the Communication and Dissemination Activities

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 <https://accting.eu>

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Disclaimer

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Table of Contents

The ACCTING project	7
Project Consortium	8
Summary	9
Introduction	10
Relation to other tasks and deliverables.....	10
Objectives	11
Target stakeholders	12
Dissemination activities	17
Knowledge dissemination	17
Support to scientific publications	17
Scientific publications	18
Public deliverables	21
Open Access.....	21
Presentations at scientific conferences	21
Community of experts and stakeholders	24
Bottom-up initiatives	24
Dissemination synergies with related projects	26
Organisation of joint events.....	28
EU Platforms.....	29
Pilot project networks	30
Advocacy	31
Promotion of ACCTING's factsheets	31
Promotion of the research agenda	43
Communication activities and channels	47
ACCTING Website.....	47
Website development.....	47
Blog entries	48
Partners' websites.....	49
Activity on social media.....	50
Campaigns.....	51
Analytics	52
Reddit	53

Electronic project newsletter	54
Press release.....	55
Monitoring and evaluation of dissemination and communication activities	56
Exploitation of results	57
Publication on repositories as open access.....	57
Pilot Actions	58
ACCTING Network.....	61
Further research	62
Policy-making	63
Appendix	66
Dataset	66
Project deliverables.....	66
Factsheets	67
Research line reports.....	68

List of Figures

Figure 1: Inspiring initiatives, individual narratives and case studies on the ACCTING website	25
Figure 2: Example of inspiring initiatives, case studies and narratives shared on social media	26
Figure 3: Sister projects' promotion of their participation at ACCTING's final conference	27
Figure 4: examples of webinars organised with or by sister projects	28
Figure 5: ACCTING featured in the GDSO newsletter	29
Figure 6: Workshop at EURESFO 2024	32
Figure 7: Promotion of ACCTING at ESF's 50th anniversary event	33
Figure 8: ACCTING blog posts on the project website:	49
Figure 9: Screenshot of ACCTING's account on X	51
Figure 10: Post introducing the Factsheets	51
Figure 11: Publication promoting the webinar series	52
Figure 12: Publication leveraging the World Food Day	52
Figure 13: Number of impressions on ACCTING's LinkedIn account	52
Figure 14: Number of clicks on ACCTING's LinkedIn publications	53
Figure 15: Number of members reached on ACCTING's LinkedIn channel	53
Figure 16: Publication on reddit	54
Figure 17: Community meeting organised within PA 1- Dialogue and action against wildfires	58
Figure 18: Overview of the videos promoting pilot projects.	61

List of Tables

Table 1: ACCTING's main objectives, target stakeholders, dissemination actions, and communication and dissemination channels.....	14
Table 2: Overview of Info Sessions.....	35
Table 3: Overview of webinars promoting the factsheets	40
Table 4: Overview of webinars promoting the research agenda.....	46

List of Acronyms

CSO	Civil society organisation
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
M	Month
NGO	Non-governmental organisations
RFO	Research funding organisation
RL	Research Line
T	Task
WP	Work Package

The ACCTING project

It is acknowledged by now that the global climate crisis is not only an ecological crisis but also an economic, social and political crisis, with devastating effects on individuals and societies. These negative effects are not evenly distributed within societies. It is the poorer, marginalised and vulnerable groups who are the most acutely affected, exacerbating existing socio-economic inequalities. The European Green Deal foresees efficient use of resources for a circular and clean economy. However, inequalities emerge in the context of its policy and interventions.

The EU-funded ACCTING project takes these considerations as a starting point for a complex series of research and experimental activities aimed at identifying, analysing and testing policies and initiatives capable of responding to this crisis, mitigating its effects on the most vulnerable and helping them play a significant role in the pursuit of greater environmental sustainability.

The project mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies and supporting behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

ACCTING explores the impact of Green Deal policy initiatives on individual and collective behaviours, provides evidence, and empowers policymakers and stakeholders to anticipate policy responses and potential negative influences, and mitigate such impacts in decision-making. The project collects new data on Green Deal policy interventions and co-designs and implements pilot actions to reduce or prevent policy-related inequalities and advance behavioural change for an inclusive and equal European Green Deal.

Project Consortium

	European Science Foundation (ESF)
	Örebro University (ORU)
	Yellow Window (YW)
	Knowledge and Innovation (K&I)
	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation (ZSI)
	Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)
	ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability, European Secretariat
	Sabancı University (SU)
	Instituto de Geografia e Ordenamento de Território (IGOT)
	South East European Research Center (SEERC)
	Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi (UAIC)
	European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)
	University of Gothenburg (UGOT)

Summary

This deliverable (D7.4) provides a comprehensive overview of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities carried out over the 40-month duration of the ACCTING project, funded under the Horizon 2020 Science with and for Society programme. ACCTING – *AdvanCing behavioural Change Through an INclusive Green deal* – aimed to address the social and economic inequalities exacerbated by the EU Green Deal through inclusive research, stakeholder engagement, and policy recommendations.

As planned in the communication and dissemination strategy (D7.1, updated in D7.5), the activities were structured around three central pillars: knowledge dissemination, the creation of a community of experts and stakeholders, and targeted advocacy. Key actions included scientific publications, policy briefs, the promotion of inspiring grassroots and individual initiatives, policy recommendations (factsheets), public deliverables, and organisation of events and webinars. Activities were tailored to diverse stakeholder groups, including policymakers, NGOs, researchers, social innovators, and the general public.

ACCTING produced a broad range of outputs, from research agendas and pilot actions to operational factsheets, that have been actively promoted across multiple channels, including social media, the project website, newsletters, conferences, and institutional networks. Over 150 inspiring practices were spotlighted, and the project organised over 20 webinars and info sessions, engaging stakeholders across Europe and beyond.

The report also details the project's exploitation pathways beyond its lifetime, ensuring that its outputs remain accessible and impactful. ACCTING's advocacy efforts have evolved into a dynamic model of sustained engagement, demonstrating that while behavioural and structural change requires time, the project has established enduring foundations for inclusive and just environmental transitions across Europe.

Introduction

Relation to other tasks and deliverables

This deliverable “Report on Communication and Dissemination Activities” (D7.4) provides an overview of the communication and dissemination activities led throughout the ACCTING project. This consolidated and public report follows the two Communication and Dissemination Strategy updates (D7.5 and D7.8) submitted in M12 and M24 respectively, which updated the initial Communication and Dissemination Strategy (D7.1) submitted in M4.

The communication activities implemented were facilitated by the promotional material described in D7.2, “Project communication toolkit”, which includes the project branding and visual identity guidelines, project website and communications materials. A description of advocacy activities is also included, following the strategy designed to promote the policy guidelines in the “Advocacy Plan for the Promotion of the Policy Guidelines” (D7.3), submitted in M16.

The Report on Communication and Dissemination Activities also addresses activities involving the ACCTING Network, the project’s central stakeholder database of European experts, researchers, practitioners, initiated as part of T2.2, then developed and maintained within T1.6, as well as synergies with other projects, led within T1.6.

More specifically, the knowledge dissemination activities leverage insights generated in WP3, and disseminated as part of a specific task (T7.3). The advocacy efforts were organised under task 7.4 focusing on the promotion of the guidelines and project results produced in WP4 and WP5, and under task 7.5 for the promotion of the research agenda produced in T5.3. The communication activities, including awareness-raising, were organised under T7.1 (Development and implementation of project communication strategy) and T7.2 (project communication toolkit development and deployment).

Objectives

The project's dissemination and communication activities were linked with ACCTING's impact objectives:

- Make the effects of the EU Green Deal and the associated policy-decisions on inequalities known to policymakers and to stakeholders; how they affect vulnerable groups; how parts of society with a less strong voice in the public debate are affected; and how new forms of discriminations and inequalities develop in the context of the Green Deal.
- Motivate policymakers to consider the impacts on inequalities when taking policy decisions related to the Green Deal and to make use of ACCTING's guidelines to anticipate impacts and potential adverse effects.
- Convince policymakers to take measures that alleviate and/or mitigate the adverse effects of Green Deal initiatives on inequalities and vulnerable groups.
- Increase the visibility of the many initiatives taken by citizens and NGOs to compensate for the Green Deal impacts on vulnerable groups and use these to inspire both NGOs and policymakers to stimulate their uptake in various contexts.
- Demonstrate the potential impact of the pilot actions developed in ACCTING and convince policymakers and other stakeholders to take similar initiatives.

The project dissemination activities were based on three central pillars:

1. **Knowledge dissemination:** to disseminate the new knowledge generated on inequalities related to Green Deal policy measures to the scientific community.
2. **Creation of the ACCTING community of experts and stakeholders:** A community of experts, researchers, practitioners and civil society organisations on behavioural, social and cultural change, was developed during the project lifetime, and involved in various project activities to ensure that the project has real impact on citizens.
3. **Advocacy:** to boost the project impact on policymaking at the different levels (national/regional/local), encouraging policy implementers, influencers and social innovators, as well as employers and NGOs to take up the results of actions and adapt/improve their actions, and ensuring that the research agenda inspires further research, paving the way towards an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal.

Target stakeholders

To achieve the communication and dissemination objectives stated above, activities targeted specific audience groups at different stages of the project. The project addressed organisations as well as individuals, approached as beneficiaries and/or end-users. The audience groups identified here were targeted for research development, as much as for the uptake of results and general awareness about the project's scope.

The stakeholders were identified in a database used by all partners to keep track of advocacy activities and reach out to more target stakeholders.

- **Policymakers**

ACCTING targeted policymakers at different levels of authority (international, European, national, regional, local), specifically working on the implementation of the Green Deal as well as those not directly involved in the implementation but with various aspects related to the Green Deal. Policy implementers, influencers, experts shaping policies are also included in this audience group. International policymakers included the World Bank and UN agencies such as UNEP, WMO, as well as the UN food and agriculture hub based in Rome which includes the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations, the UN World Food Programme, and the International Fund for Agricultural Development headquarters. The key policy stakeholders at the EU level are members of the European Commission (i.e. DG ENV, DG EMPL), the Council of the EU, and the European Parliament (i.e. Committee on Environment, Public Health and Food Safety - ENVI). At the national, regional and local levels, our emphasis involved working with government bodies and agencies responsible for environmental and social policies and initiatives ensuring an approach that aligns with the Green Deal objectives and addresses specific regional and local challenges.

- **NGOs, charities, associations at EU and national levels**

The dissemination activities targeted organisations at national and EU levels who could potentially develop initiatives that encouraged vulnerable groups to adapt their behaviour to climate change. These could be NGOs and European level associations of NGOs or associations working with vulnerable groups of society among whom Green Deal impacts can lead to increased inequalities and discrimination, on the basis of race/ethnicity, nationality, class, caste, creed, colour, religion, belief, gender, language, sexual orientation, gender identity, sex characteristics, age, health or/and other status.

The project's communication activities towards this audience group leveraged on alliances with EU-level umbrella organisations, as well as the network built with the identified organisations mapped within WP2 for their existing initiatives.

- **Research Funding Organisations**

Research funding organisations (RFOs) and European level associations of RFOs constituted a specific target audience for the promotion of the research agenda. They were reached through partners' networks, namely the regional-level RFO network developed within the SUPERA project

and now maintained by the GENDERACTIONplus project, as well as through EU-level umbrella organisations, such as Science Europe

- **Researchers, research community**

ACCTING targeted the scientific community involved in research fields related to the Green Deal, marginalised groups, gender inequalities, and the project's eight research lines. Examples of relevant groups that were identified include, among others, the International Sociological Association, the European Political Science Consortium, SCORAI (Sustainable Consumption Research and Action Initiative) and similar European projects and initiatives.

- **Employers, Enterprises, business sector**

Enterprises, associations of employers, employers in public and private sectors, with specific focus on employers of vulnerable groups were targeted for the promotion of the factsheets. These may include European-level associations and organisations related to this broad area (i.e. Business Europe) but also to more specific organisations and institutions related to specific Green Deal policy areas (i.e. FoodDrinkEurope).

- **Social innovators**

Our aim has been to connect with innovators and their pioneering novel approaches and solutions, These social innovators play a significant role in transforming societal responses to climate change, promoting gender equality and empowering vulnerable groups. These social innovators have been addressed to participate in the pilot actions, and their work has been promoted through the identification and use of Bottom-up initiatives.

- **Public in general**

Each target stakeholder group was approached to achieve a specific communication and dissemination objective, with key messages and specific actions through various channels. The table hereafter offers an overview of how the dissemination activities were planned.

Table 1: ACCTING’s main objectives, target stakeholders, dissemination actions, and communication and dissemination channels

Objectives	Target stakeholders	Key messages	Dissemination actions	Communication and Dissemination Channels
<p>Make the effects of the EU Green Deal and the associated policy decisions on inequalities known.</p>	<p>All target groups: Policymakers, NGOs, CSOs, business sector, citizens, social innovators, media; Research community, RFOs, sister projects.</p>	<p>Policies related to the Green Deal can have considerable negative impacts on vulnerable groups. ACCTING is generating knowledge on the impact of the Green Deal on vulnerable groups, focusing on eight research lines. Further research on the identified knowledge gaps is needed.</p>	<p>Promotion of the research lines, results of research activities, factsheets, research agenda Scientific publications, presentations at events, webinars, joint with sister projects</p>	<p>Regular posting on project website and engagement on social media Press releases Newsletters Synergies with sister projects Webinars Final conference Events: conference, panel discussions, webinars Zenodo Community</p>
<p>Increase the visibility of the many initiatives taken by citizens and NGOs to compensate for the Green Deal impacts on vulnerable groups and</p>	<p>Citizens, social entrepreneurs, NGOs, local authorities, policymakers</p>	<p>Many societal initiatives mitigate the Green Deal impacts on vulnerable groups. They go to show how vulnerable groups can be</p>	<p>Showcase inspiring initiatives, link with policymakers</p>	<p>Dedicated section on project website, regular posts, engagement on social media and high-reach blogs. Participation in national and local events</p>

Objectives	Target stakeholders	Key messages	Dissemination actions	Communication and Dissemination Channels
use these to inspire both NGOs and policymakers to stimulate their uptake by more citizens, regions and countries.		<p>considered in policy decisions.</p> <p>These initiatives can serve as a means of inspiration to develop other ones.</p>		<p>Newsletters</p> <p>Webinars</p> <p>Final conference</p>
Motivate policymakers to consider the impacts on inequalities when taking policy decisions related to the Green Deal and to use ACCTING's guidelines to anticipate impacts and potential adverse effects.	Policymakers at international, European, national, regional, local levels, NGOs, associations at EU and national levels, employers, media	<p>Impacts on vulnerable groups are considerable and can be avoided, anticipated and remediated.</p> <p>ACCTING's operational factsheets and pilot actions provide proof-of-concept.</p>	Promote operational factsheets developed within the project	<p>Dedicated section on project website, regular posts, engagement on social media and high-reach blogs;</p> <p>Participation in events;</p> <p>Synergies with sister projects;</p> <p>Newsletters;</p> <p>Webinars;</p> <p>Final conference</p>
Convince policymakers to take measures that alleviate and/or mitigate the adverse effects of Green Deal initiatives on inequalities and vulnerable groups.	Policymakers at international, European, national, regional, local levels, Experts shaping Green Deal policies, Employers	<p>Impacts on vulnerable group must be anticipated, alleviated, mitigated.</p> <p>ACCTING's operational factsheets and pilot actions provide proof-of-concept.</p> <p><i>The messages, actions and channels to reach this objective were detailed in the "Advocacy Plan for the</i></p>	<p>Promote operational factsheets developed within the project,</p> <p>Demonstrate full potential of project factsheets through pilot actions.</p>	<p>Dedicated section on project website, regular posts, engagement on social media and high-reach blogs;</p> <p>Participation in events</p> <p>Pilot projects' network;</p> <p>Synergies with sister projects;</p> <p>Newsletters;</p>

Objectives	Target stakeholders	Key messages	Dissemination actions	Communication and Dissemination Channels
		<i>Promotion of the Policy Guidelines” (D7.3)</i>		Webinars; Final conference
Demonstrate the potential impact of the pilot actions developed in ACCTING and convince policymakers and other stakeholders to take similar initiatives.	Policymakers at international, European, national, regional, local levels, Experts shaping Green Deal policies, Employers	ACCTING’s pilot actions provide proof-of-concept of how impacts on vulnerable groups stemming from Green Deal policies can be anticipated and remediated.	Demonstrate potential of pilot actions to be scaled up.	Dedicated section on project website, regular posts, engagement on social media and high-reach blogs; Pilot projects’ channels and network; Newsletters; Final conference

Dissemination activities

The description of the project dissemination activities is based on the three central pillars mentioned in the introduction: knowledge dissemination, the creation of a community of experts and stakeholders, and advocacy.

Knowledge dissemination

The following activities consisted in producing and promoting the knowledge developed within the project, and included scientific publications per se, activities to enable progress on these, and participation in scientific conferences. They aimed at filling in the research gaps on the impact of Green Deal policy initiatives on changes in the individual and collective behaviours, with particular attention to those of vulnerable groups, and their effect on inequalities in the EU, based on a multidimensional gendered and intersectional framework.

Support to scientific publications

Based on the new knowledge generated on the impact on inequalities and vulnerable groups and the role played by policy decisions, the project's consortium had an ambitious plan to submit 20 scientific publications by the end of the project. To support partners in their publication efforts, a set of six internal seminars were organised online to strengthen the consortium's knowledge base on specific topics and two paper seminars were held to advance the project's publication plan.

- **Paper seminar: First research cycle, 30 May 2022**

To coordinate the research within each line and stimulate collaborations within and between lines, a half-day conference was organised by the task leader (ORU/UGOT) and involving all research line leaders and partners involved in the experimental case studies.

- **Feminist Methodologies, 9 September 2022**

With Professor Joni Seager, Professor Ayse Gül Altınay and Professor Sofia Strid. This seminar explored the ways in which intersectional/gender+ feminist methodologies can improve research, policy directions and outcomes, in the context of the Green Deal and beyond.

- **Sustainability and transformative change, 11 July 2022**

With Magnus Boström, Professor of Sociology, Örebro University, Sweden

- **Introduction to Narrative Analysis, 20 June 2022**

Introduction to narrative analysis, followed by session on constructing narrative reports. With Marina Cacace, Senior Researcher, Knowledge & Innovation

- **Introduction to Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA), 23 March 2023**

With Marina Cacace, Senior Researcher, Knowledge & Innovation

- **Paper Symposium, 11 February 2025**

The primary purpose of this symposium was to help generate and strengthen the development of publishable academic papers. It was also an opportunity to share research results and create synergies between research lines, generating discussions and exploring opportunities for further collaboration. The invitation of this seminar was extended to the Shared Green Deal, PHOENIX and Real Deal projects, whose members acted as discussants.

Scientific publications

At the time of the publication of this deliverable, the following articles have been published and submitted. More papers are currently being drafted, to be submitted before the end of the project's lifetime.

Articles (published)

1. Boostani, P., Pellegrini-Masini, G., & Klein, J. (2024). The role of community energy schemes in reducing energy poverty and promoting social inclusion: A systematic literature review. *Energies*, 17(13), 3232. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en17133232>

Articles and book chapters (submitted)

2. Abrantes, P., Moreno, L., & Fonseca, M. L. (2025). Designing intersectional gender+ research: Insights from a European study on food security and marginalised populations. Submitted to *Sage Research Methods*.
3. Abrantes, P., Moreno, L., Fonseca, M. L., Borhan Türeli, B., Stergiadis, C., Szüdi, G., Zorell, C., & Gajdusek, M. F. (2025). Inclusive Governance for Urban Food Security: Lessons from Community Gardens in European Cities. Submitted to *City and Environment Interactions*.
4. Balkmar, D. (2025). Negotiating car dependency: Conditions and potential for sustainable mobility transitions among families experiencing transport disadvantage. Submitted to *Travel Behaviour and Society*.
5. Balkmar, D., Sandström, L., Esteves, A., Fonseca, M. L., Holman, A., Popusoi, S., & Pugliese, F. (2025). Commoning cycling: Grass-root initiatives for inclusive mobility transitions among people facing barriers to cycling. Submitted to *Transport Research Record*.
6. Boostani, P., Pellegrini Masini, G., & Klein, J. (2025). Barriers and drivers of participation in energy communities: Towards inclusive energy communities in Norway and Denmark. Submitted to *Energy, Sustainability and Society*.
7. Boostani, P., Pellegrini Masini, G., & Carnevale, A. (2025). Energy vulnerability in Norway: Can energy communities help? Submitted to *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities*.
8. Boström, M., Strid, S., Zorell, C., & Balkmar, D. (2025). Developing action capacity for sufficient consumption among Europeans facing unequal conditions. Submitted to *Frontiers in Sustainability*.

9. Türeli, B. B., Düzel, E., & Altınay, A. G. (2025). The Soil and The City: Gendered Empowerment in Community Gardens in Izmir, Turkey. Submitted to *Antipode*.
10. Chatzimpyros, V., Vivas A.B., Stergiadis., C., Borhan Tureli., B., Holman, A., Popusoi, S., & Zorell, C. (2025). Values associated with ESFC as a function of social vulnerability to the green deal: Insights from narrative interviews from five countries in Europe. Submitted to *Food, Culture and Society*.
11. Celebi, D., Botha, D., Cacace, M., Niethammer, J., Quinti, G., Tzamouranou, E., & Strid, S. (2025). Building resilient communities against wildfires through participatory methods: Insights from Messinia, Greece. Submitted to *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*.
12. Celebi, D., Botha, D., Cacace, M., Niethammer, J., & Quinti, G. (2025). Unlocking local potential: A comparative analysis of bottom-up initiatives driving the Green Deal transformation. Submitted to *Nature Climate Change*.
13. Türel, B., Düzel, E., & Altınay, A. G. (2025). The soil and the city: Gendered empowerment in community gardens in Izmir, Turkey. Under submission to *Frontiers*.
14. Fonseca, M. L. (in press). Voluntariado Jovem na Conservação e Restauro Ambiental: O Caso do Projeto Natura Observa em Cascais. In F. Cravidão, N. Santos, L. Dimuccio, P. Nossa & R. Jacinto (Eds.), *Estudos em Homenagem a Lúcio Cunha*, Imprensa da Universidade de Coimbra.
15. Fonseca, M. L., & Esteves, A. (2025). Pathways to inclusive cycling: Overcoming barriers and promoting equitable mobility in Lisbon's vulnerable neighbourhoods. Submitted to *Cities: The International Journal of Urban Policy and Planning*.
16. Fonseca, M. L., & Esteves, A. (in press). Pobreza e mobilidade sustentável: Facilitadores e obstáculos de um sistema inclusivo de mobilidade ciclável em Lisboa. In E. Brito-Henriques, E. Marques da Costa, & P. Abrantes (Eds.), *Planeamento territorial e turismo: Estudos em homenagem a José Manuel Simões*. Edições CEG: Universidade de Lisboa.
17. Fonseca, M. L., & Moreno, L. (accepted). Hortas Urbanas e Segurança Alimentar de Grupos Vulneráveis: o caso do Parque Agrícola da Alta de Lisboa. In M. Padeiro, J. Ferrão, R. Almendra & A. Freitas (Eds.), *Livro de Homenagem a Paula Santana*, Imprensa da Universidade de Coimbra.
18. Quinti, G., & Marta, F. (2025). Climate change mitigation and adaptation policies: Addressing unintended effects on inequalities. Submitted to *Social Sciences*.
19. Sandström, L. (2025). Sustainable transport for all? Inequality and resistance to car free policies. Submitted to *Environmental Sociology*.
20. Stergiadis, C., Celebi, D., Klados, M., Zaharis, N., Abrantes, P., Balkmar, D., Cacace, M., Pugliese, F., Esteves, A., Gajdusek, M.F., Fonseca, M. L., Pellegrini Masini, G., Moreno, L., Quinti, G., Strid, S., Vivas, A., & White, J. (2025). Building a just green future: Research directions for inclusive sustainability in Europe. Submitted to *Sustainability Science*.
21. Strid, S., Zorell, C., & Boström, M. (2025). Enablers and barriers for behavioural change towards sustainable lifestyles and the green transition. Submitted to *Sustainability: Science, Practice and Policy*.

22. Vivas, A. B., Chatzimpyros V., Stergiadis, C., Borhan Türeli, B., Holman, A., Popusoi, S., & Zorell, C. (2025). The potential of bottom-up initiatives to produce a just transformation towards sustainable food consumption. Submitted to *Journal of Agriculture, Food Systems, and Community Development*.
23. White, J., Green, C., & Düzel, E. (2025). Vulnerable knowledge: Responding to the uncertainties of climate-change-related disaster. Submitted to *Disasters*.
24. Zorell, C. (2025). Harmonising health and food security in marginalised communities. In: I. Petrikova, J. Cole, & A. Thampi (Eds.), *Handbook of the Politics of Food Security - Through the Lens of Planetary Health Ethics*. Berlin: De Gruyter.
25. Zorell, C., Strid, S., & Boström, M. (2025). Rethinking norms of citizenship in sustainability transformations. Submitted to *Environmental Politics*.

Articles (under internal peer review)

26. Balkmar, D. (2025). 'We never stop cycling': Trike bike schools' impact on active travel and cycling inclusion. Under preparation for special issue on 'Disability and Cycling' in *Active Travel Studies*.
27. Boostani, P., Vilhelmsen, K., Pellegrini-Masini, G., Quinti, G., & Pugliese, F. (2025). Do inclusive energy communities enable behavioural and social change? Insights from cases in Denmark, Italy and Norway. Potentially for *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities*.
28. Cacace, M., Marta, F., Pugliese, F., d'Andrea L., Quinti (2025). Identifying Patterns of Inclusive Change in Sustainability Transitions through Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA). Under preparation for *Forum: Qualitative Social Research*
29. Gajdusek, M. F., Szüdi, G, Pro-environmental action in 5 European countries: Knowledge processes and transformative change in vulnerable settings
30. Humbert, A. L., Zorell, C., Küchler, F., & Strid, S. (2025). Enablers and hindrances towards a green transition. A quantitative intersectional analysis. Under preparation for *Sustainability*.
31. Pellegrini, G., Boostani, P., Carnevale, A., Gehlmann, F., Klöckner, C., & Vilhelmsen, K., (2025). Bottom-up initiatives for an inclusive green transition: What is their role and what challenges they face? Advanced draft for *Energy Research and Social Science*.
32. Pugliese, F., Cacace, M., Sandström, L., Balkmar D., L., Esteves, A., Fonseca, M. L., Holman, A., Popusoi, S., (2025). Right to Clean Air or Car Use? Intersectional Responses to Car-Restrictive Policies in the Context of a Just Transition. Advanced Draft for *Local Environment*.
33. Quinti. G., Denis, A., Hilman, A., Kerremans, A., Propusoi, S.(2025). Environmental sustainability and vulnerability: the case of micro-enterprises led by disadvantaged entrepreneurs. Advanced draft for *Materials & Techniques*.

Target: 20 scientific articles, papers or publications submitted

Achieved: 25 scientific papers and book chapters submitted, 8 more to be submitted.

Public deliverables

ACCTING research activities aimed at feeding the co-creation of solutions and recommendations, as well as the project's next research cycle. Next to the production of scientific articles and the research agenda, research has also resulted in the publication of data sets, reports, and peer-reviewed public deliverables (see appendix).

Open Access

ACCTING has followed the Green Open Access model which allows for self-archiving and free public access as a standard approach. Reports, data sets, and public deliverables have been uploaded onto Zenodo (Open access repository) by the ESF, which allows to assign a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to any type of project outcome. A [Zenodo "ACCTING community"](#), also curated by ESF, gathers all the publications developed within the project.

The project's research accessibility is developed in full details in D1.2 "Data Management Plan", updated in D1.4 (M40) which outlines the procedures for collecting or generating data, securing storage, sharing, archiving, and preserving the data sets generated by the project.

Public deliverables are also linked on the project website and actively promoted through ACCTING's dissemination channels. Partners were encouraged to actively participate in the promotion of these insights using their institutional channels. Authors were encouraged to share them on their personal profiles on the ResearchGate portal, on their Academia or LinkedIn profiles, with full acknowledgement of the project.

Presentations at scientific conferences

ACCTING's scientific outputs were shared with the scientific community through participation at scientific conferences at international, national, and institutional levels, through presentations, participation in panel discussions and seminars.

International conferences

- Abrantes, P., Zorell C., Moreno, L. (2024) Narratives of change: More than individual intentions in the path to a sustainable and socially just food future. *AESOP Sustainable Food Planning Conference 2024. Proceedings*. AESOP4Food, 2024.
- Abrantes, P., Moreno, L., Fonseca, M. L., & Ferreira, D. (2024). A promoção da segurança alimentar e de dietas saudáveis em comunidades vulneráveis: desafios na região de Lisboa (Portugal), em contexto europeu - III Congresso de Geografia da Saúde dos Países de Língua Portuguesa, Geosaúde 2024.
- Zorell, C. (2023). Avenues to make sustainable food consumption less socially unequal [Presentation]. *General Conference of the European Consortium of Political Research*, Örebro, Sweden.
- Balkmar, D. (2023). Cycling against all odds: Families everyday struggles for cycling in socially vulnerable and transport disadvantaged areas [Paper presentation]. *'Critical Tensions in*

Planning for Cycling, *Cycling and Society Research Group Annual Symposium 2023*, Dublin, Ireland.

- Boostani, P. (2023). "The role of community energy schemes in reducing energy vulnerability across Europe; A systematic literature review" [Paper presentation]. *The RGS-IBG Annual International Conference 2023*, London, UK.
 - Boostani, P. (2023). A systematic review of community energy schemes through a feminist perspective on the energy transition [Paper presentation]. *Second International Conference on New Pathways for a Just and Inclusive Energy Transition: Connecting Multiple Stakeholders and Levels*, Groningen, The Netherlands.
 - Fonseca, M. L., Moreno, L., & Abrantes, P. (2025) Food Practices Among Vulnerable Populations: Enablers and Constraints for Sustainable and Healthy Diets (Presentation) *10th EUGEO Congress 2025 – Geographies of a Changing Europe*, Vienna, 8-11 September (Accepted).
 - Strid, S. (2024). For an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal: Integrating gendered and intersectional perspectives in Green Deal policies. [presentation]. *Global Accessibility Awareness Day*, online.
 - Strid, S. (2024). Cocreation for solutions to wicked problems [paper presentation]. *IMIN: Impact Innovation Summit 2024*, Helsingborg Arena, Sweden.
 - Fonseca, M. L., Esteves, A., & Ferreira, D. (2024). Transport poverty and sustainable travel: enablers and hinders of an inclusive cycling mobility system in Lisbon [Presentation]. *35th International Geographical Congress*, Dublin, Ireland.
 - Moreno, L., Abrantes, P., Fonseca, M. L., & Ferreira, D. (2024). Green Horizons: Fostering Food Security and Sustainability in Vulnerable European Communities [Presentation]. *XVIII International Seminars on the Overarching Issues of the European Area*, Porto, Portugal.
 - Balkmar, D (2024) Interventions for cycling inclusion: cycling initiatives for an inclusive mobility transition in the EU. [Paper presentation], *Cycling & Society*, Porto, Portugal.
 - White, J., & Düzel, E. (2023). The continuum of disaster: feeling, perceiving and anticipating more-than-human change at Europe's periphery. *Pollen Political Ecology Conference*, Lund, Sweden.
 - Gajdusek, M. (2025). Local vulnerabilities and pro-nature action in ACCTING.eu and experimental patterns for citizen involvement in DANUBE4all [Paper Presentation]. *45th conference of the International Association for Danube Research (IAD)*, Sofia, Bulgaria.
- Conceição, C., Vasconcelos, J., & Fragoso, M. (2024). Indoor thermal discomfort and vulnerability to cold in a precarious housing neighbourhood in Lisbon [Presentation]. *35th International Geographical Congress 2024*, Dublin, Ireland. [session C.23: Health and Environment: Urban environment for healthy ageing].

Organisation of an ACCTING Panel: "Towards a fair and inclusive Green Deal: Insights from European research", *Green Digital Accessibility 2024*, Barcelona and Online. Presentations included:

- Düzel, E., & Borhan Türeli, B. (2024). Planes and Goats: Imagining a Multispecies Response to Disasters in the Age of Techno-fixes
- Pugliese, F., & Cacace, M. (2024). Right to clean air or freedom of private transport? The dilemma of European car-free policies from diverse perspectives of vulnerable social groups
- Zorell, C. (2024). Access and inaccessibility to healthy and environmentally sustainable food in marginalised communities

National conferences

- Strid, S. (2021). Gender, sustainability and transformative change: feminist perspectives on crises [Presentation]. Sustainability Conference, Örebro, Sweden
- Fonseca, M. L. (2023). Cohesion and Territorial Planning: challenges for the future of Portugal [Presentation]. XIV Congress of Portuguese Geographers: Territories in transition and sustainability: Crises and responses, Lisbon, Portugal.
- Marques da Costa, N., Esteves, A., & Ferreira, D. (2023). The lack of transport and the Covid 19 pandemic and post-pandemic period: Behavioural change in individual mobility in the Lisbon region [Paper presentation]. XIV Congress of Portuguese Geographers: Territories in transition and sustainability: Crises and responses, Lisbon, Portugal.
- Vasconcelos, J., & Fragoso, M. (2023). Narratives about behavioural changes in the face of natural disasters by the vulnerable population. [Paper presentation]. *XIV Congress of Portuguese Geographers: Territories in transition and sustainability: Crises and responses, Lisbon, Portugal*. Book of abstracts, p. 268. ISBN: 978-989-99244-9-9. Ed. Associação Portuguesa de Geógrafos / IGOT-ULisboa, November 2023.
- Fonseca, M. L., & Esteves, A. (2024). Pobreza e mobilidade sustentável: facilitadores e obstáculos a um sistema inclusivo de mobilidade ciclável em Lisboa [Paper presentation]. *XVIII Iberian Colloquium on Geography – Societal challenges: the perspective of Geography*, Coimbra, Portugal.

Institutional workshops and seminars

- Strid, S. (2022). Gendered inequalities: Findings from research projects on violence, crisis, and sustainability [Seminar]. Sociology Higher Seminar, UGOT, Gothenburg, Sweden.
- Pellegrini Masini, G. (2023). Community energy schemes to fight energy poverty: insights from the ongoing ACCTING project [Workshop] Good engagement in the energy transition? - NTNU Energy Transition Week 2023, Norwegian University of Science and Technology NTNU, Trondheim.
- Fonseca, M. L., Abrantes, P., Moreno, L., & Ferreira, D. (2024). Environmental Protection, Food Security, and Healthy Diets in Vulnerable Populations: Catalysts and Barriers to Behaviour Change [workshop]. 1st LT5 Workshop & World Café of the lab. TERRA - Landscape and environmental restoration in Portugal. Lisbon, Portugal.

- Zorell, C. (2024). Harmonising planetary health and food security in marginalised communities of the Global North [workshop]. Food security workshop, Royal Holloway University London, United Kingdom.
- Celebi, D. (2025). A Green Future: Community action and inclusion. York Festival of Ideas, York, United Kingdom.

Community of experts and stakeholders

ACCTING's dissemination efforts were enhanced by regular engagement with a substantial network developed through the project, comprising:

- ACCTING's consortium members' networks, including two network organisations (ICLEI and ECSA)
- National researchers participating in the research activities,
- External experts and researchers contributing to the Open Studios in WP4,
- Pilot action participants in WP5,
- Representatives from projects funded under the same call or with a similar scope,
- European key stakeholders, such as local governments and municipalities, research funding organisations and further European network organisations,
- Representatives from selected NGOs, civil society organisations involved in behavioural, social and cultural change and mapped within T2.2 for their inspiring initiatives. They were approached and engaged to follow the project's developments.

These stakeholders were invited to join the network through [the project website interface](#) and received project news and updates following their expressed interest, complying to GDPR standards. They were also engaged through bilateral contacts with partners. The following section describes specific dissemination and engagement efforts with these community members. The exploitation of these contacts is described under the Exploitation section.

Bottom-up initiatives

A selection of inspiring initiatives supporting Green Deal actions were spotlighted through publication on the project website and promotion on social media, giving online visibility to a broad array of “better stories” of positive involvement of society, and more specifically marginalised groups, in response to climate change.

These bottom-up initiatives from NGOs, civil society organisations, mapped within T2.2 and analysed in 2.3, as well as anonymised narratives stemming from qualitative research activities, are showcased on the project website, categorised by research line and by country. There are currently 152 inspiring initiatives published on the project website.

While providing its audience with inspiration for positive change, the promotion of bottom-up initiatives provided an opportunity to engage with the CSOs and NGOs featured in these stories for dissemination of other outputs from ACCTING.

Figure 1: Inspiring initiatives, individual narratives and case studies on the ACCTING website

Figure 2: Example of inspiring initiatives, case studies and narratives shared on social media

Target: 150 inspiring practices promoted on the project website

Achieved: 152 inspiring practices promoted on the project website

Dissemination synergies with related projects

Leveraging the mapping of related initiatives under T1.6, ACCTING engaged in bilateral contacts with projects funded under the same call or similar programmes with the aim of developing synergies to support the project's dissemination activities.

Project's communication channels

ACCTING was featured on the following websites:

- Shared Green Deal: [featured on their website and in newsletters](#)
- [Mobi-Twin](#): promoted on their website
- [R&I policy making, implementation and support in the West Balkans](#)
- [Socio-Bee](#)
- [EERA-E3S](#)

Poster presentations at ACCTING's final conference

In addition to the ACCTING Pilot Projects who presented their results during the poster exhibition, the following projects and initiatives responded to the open call to present their research results at ACCTING's final conference, promoting their participation to the event within their network.

- [CO-VALUE](#)

- [MOBI-TWIN](#)
- [ST4TE](#)
- [FITTER-EU](#)
- [Urban ReLeaf](#)
- [VERITY](#)
- [Giants of the Lagoon](#)
- [LISTEN: Learning and Inclusion for Sustainable Community Engagement](#)
- INSPIRE: Supporting the inclusion, well-being, and growth of rural areas through multi-actor Smart Villages labs for enhanced governance frameworks
- [Empowering Teachers for the Green and Digital Transition](#)
- [Leveraging Partnerships for Energy Justice: Lessons from New York and California for the EU](#)
- [Laou Laou: Reclaiming Public Space Through Sustainable Mobility and Community Engagement](#)
- Imagining Inclusive Open Spaces (LiDD École de Design, LITL Laboratoire Interdisciplinaire des Transitions de Lille)

Figure 3: Screenshot of sister projects' promotion of their participation at ACCTING's final conference

Organisation of joint webinars with sister projects

ACCTING **organised** the following webinars involving sister projects:

- “[Engaging vulnerable groups in building resilient futures](#)”, co-organised with Futuresilience and Regions4Climate.
- “[Building resilience to natural disasters: Valorising local communities and solidarity networks](#)”, organised as an EU Green Week 2024 partner event with the participation of GreenSCENT
- Three ACCTING webinars were set up as *Community Conversations* in a collaboration with ICLEI’s [Urban Community for Sustainable and Just Cities](#): “Marginalised communities’ access to healthy and sustainable food”, “Building a civil society in solidarity with marginalized groups for greater social impact” and “Funding support for bottom-up initiatives”, in discussion with the following projects and organisations: [Pervolarides in Thessaloniki](#), [ECOLISE](#)’s [COM4LGD](#), [Roof Coliving](#). The contents are further described in the Advocacy section.

These webinars have been included in a [playlist of webinars](#) featured on ACCTING’s YouTube channel.

Figure 4: examples of webinars organised with or by sister projects

ACCTING was also **invited** to share project insights in the following webinar organised by sister project GreenSCENT: “[Ensuring an inclusive and accessible transition](#)” organised on Global Accessibility Day 2024 with [ClearClimate](#), [IChange](#), [Rethink Action](#), and [GreenTeens](#) projects.

Synergies were also sought with the [GenderACTION+](#) project to disseminate the webinars promoting the research agendas to research funding organisations, as detailed in the Advocacy section hereafter.

Organisation of joint events

- Sister projects [Adaptation AGORA](#) and [Urban ReLeaf](#) joined ACCTING in organising a workshop on “Co-creating inclusive climate adaptation solutions” within EUROSFO 2024 (detailed in Advocacy section).

EU Platforms

- The [Rural Pact Community Platform](#) disseminated ACCTING's call for pilot projects
- **The EU's Research & Innovation's Green Deal Projects Support Office**

The Green Deal Projects Support Office, and particularly the Communication and outreach working group, provided valuable support to find connections with similar initiatives and activities led at national and regional level, to create liaisons with stakeholder associations, and more generally to receive advice on stakeholder engagement.

ACCTING was presented:

- on the dedicated microsite within the [EU's Research & Innovation website](#)
- on the [CIRCABC platform](#) for the programme, for effective collaboration through networking and knowledge sharing
- in the dedicated events section were ACCTING webinars regularly featured and the Final Conference was announced
- in GDSO newsletter issues

The CIRCABC platform is used as an online dissemination tool. News and updates regarding the ACCTING project are posted in the forum, while and events and webinars are added to the collective agenda.

Figure 5: ACCTING featured in the GDSO newsletter

A “success story” was also submitted in M40 to be featured in the next issue of the GDSO newsletter and on the [dedicated section of the website](#). It highlights ACCTING’s pilot projects as inspiring examples of inclusive, community-driven solutions to advance behavioural change.

Pilot project networks

The ten pilot projects funded by ACCTING considerably supported the reach of ACCTING results. Each pilot project disseminated their outputs to their networks, acknowledging and presenting the ACCTING project. Real synergies were built with pilot project representatives attending the Final Conference and presenting their experiences and project results at multiple ACCTING webinars.

Exploitation pathways of the pilot project networks are further detailed under the Exploitation section.

Pilot Action	Dissemination activities
<p>PA1: Dialogue & Action Against Wildfires: Empowering Communities for Disaster Resilience Led by Dock in Greece</p>	<p>The organisation of a two-day forum in a town hall gathered public authority representatives, CSOs and diverse stakeholders from the four villages. This led to media coverage in local publications and on the Heinrich Böll Foundation website.</p> <p>Extensive activity on social media activity (2.1K followers), promoting disaster scenarios and policy recommendations.</p>
<p>PA2: Echoversity Led by EcoMuseum Zagori in Greece.</p>	<p>An exhibition on local biodiversity, “Weaving Network” travelled across four cities and was integrated into festivities around the European Wool Day and the European Heritage Days.</p> <p>750 participants were involved in awareness-raising events (workshops)</p> <p>200 school children were engaged in an educational programme</p> <p>Social media activity (3.4K followers), articles in local newspapers</p>
<p>PA3: Premios inclusivECs: impulsando comunidades Inclusivas Led by La Corriente, Spain</p>	<p>Campaign on social media with 20K views, 30 participants in the final award ceremony, 5 articles in press media, policy brief promoted among Spanish decision-makers</p>
<p>PA4: Supporting Roma micro-entrepreneurs in Albania towards better environmental sustainability Led by Institute of Romani Culture in Albania</p>	<p>Organisation of local meetings and training activities (68 participants); social media activities (450+ followers); development of a dedicated website, hosted beyond the project.</p>
<p>PA5: Mapko Connects Community Gardens, Led by Kokoza in the Czech Republic</p>	<p>The platform attracted over 6,500 users in 2024, with ~201 monthly user interactions. The PA was featured in Kokoza’s newsletters (5K subscribers), promoted in events, and a social media campaign targeted their 13K followers and reached 30 NGOs and 5 municipalities.</p>
<p>PA6: Food4Schools (F4S) Led by Mamegea, Greece</p>	<p>Organisation of participatory workshops, dissemination of the toolkit, press releases, video</p>

	production, interviews, and social media activity (6K followers)
PA7: Edu Move: Boosting Bike Use in Suburban Tirana Led by Active Mobility, Albania	Awareness campaign (1000 flyers distributed, street banners, social media campaign) Production of educational videos
PA8: Todas en bici, Led by aqui SCCL, Spain	Public outreach events, mixed media communication activities (blog posts, podcasts, radio interviews) including social media (900+ followers)
PA9: Get involved!, Led by Young Researchers of Serbia/	Mixed media (website, newsletters, TV and radio) including social media activity (19K followers), organisation of events. Creation of a website platform
PA10: School Goes Green, Led by Per Esempio Onlus, Italy	Production of a video (152 views), podcasts, organisation of an event, social media activity (5.2K followers)

Table 2: Overview of dissemination activities planned by pilot projects

Advocacy

Promotion of ACCTING's factsheets

To maximise impact, ACCTING's policy recommendations, submitted as D5.1 in M18 and D5.4 in M36, were published as thirteen standalone documents – formalised as factsheets presenting the main findings from the different insight-generating activities, as well as examples of inspiring practices, and operational recommendations.

For each factsheet, target audiences were defined. The factsheets were promoted among policy makers and their advisers at the national, regional and local levels, among civil society organisations involved in defending rights and providing services to vulnerable groups of society, as well as associations of professions most likely to be affected by Green Deal policies, among employers (private and public sectors),

and associations of employers.

To ensure an effective and strong uptake of ACCTING's policy guidelines, a detailed advocacy plan (D7.3) was delivered in M16. It addresses the different types and levels of stakeholders (EU, national, regional) and takes into account the variety of national or regional policy contexts. Following a consortium-wide briefing session led by Yellow Window, all partners were invited to design and

implement individual national advocacy strategies and to document progress via a shared monitoring tool and stakeholder contact database.

Four dedicated progress meetings (online in April, May and September 2024 – a physical meeting in Vienna in January 2025) allowed partners to exchange updates, successes and challenges, revealing a dynamic and evolving landscape of advocacy practice. One of the key shifts between the first and second sets of factsheets was a move away from passive dissemination toward active, dialogic engagement: rather than merely distributing factsheets, partners began hosting workshops, embedding recommendations into local processes, and aligning efforts with political calendars and opportunities.

Figure 6: Workshop at EURESFO 2024

- ICLEI advanced the advocacy agenda at the EU and local levels through strategic participation in the Urban Agenda of the EU Cities of Equality Partnership, the European Urban Resilience Forum (EURESFO) in Valencia, the European Conference of Sustainable Cities & Towns (ESCT) in Aalborg, as well as participation in consultations on the Just Transition priority of the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the EU. They integrated ACCTING messages into policy debates to push for framework conditions that enable a just and inclusive local implementation of Green Deal policies generally and particularly around biodiversity,

food systems, and climate resilience. They also co-designed interactive sessions that drew on ACCTING's pilot experiences to strengthen sustainable funding and effective collaboration mechanisms for community-led transition processes.

- In Greece, SEERC engaged a regional agrotech cluster to promote the sustainable food factsheet and entered into dialogue with municipalities in the wider Thessaloniki area. These discussions led to plans for meetings with city representatives and NGOs. SEERC also collaborated with an NGO incubator in Athens in order to promote relevant factsheets to CSOs in Greece through the incubator's extensive network as part of a broader advocacy campaign. Factsheets on CSR policies and “empowering employees to address climate change” were presented in the Thessaloniki Money Show on 14 March 2025 to a number of industry representatives. Also, SEERC organised a [local webinar \(in Greek\) on 9 April 2025](#), which gathered 30 participants and is online available at SEERC's YouTube channel.
- In Turkey, Sabancı University and the EarthSky Solidarity Association led an ambitious programme of contextualisation and engagement. They translated and adapted factsheets such as “Local is Beautiful” and “Valuing Indigenous Knowledge,” and developed visual advocacy materials tailored to municipal audiences. Advocacy activities included radio broadcasts with grassroots actors in İzmir, the organisation of public events on forest fire preparedness, and outreach to newly elected municipal administrations.
- K&I, based in Italy, integrated ACCTING findings into dialogues with local authorities and civil society organisations through workshops on

energy and solidarity communities, just transition and urban mobility. K&I had regular interactions with various councillors and officials from the Municipality of Rome and several districts in the metropolitan area of Rome regarding the social objectives of energy communities and the involvement of disadvantaged populations in urban mobility policies. K&I has also actively participated for over a year and a half in the Rome and Lazio Coordination of Renewable and Solidarity Energy Communities, including 216 members, among them energy community leaders, officials from the municipality and districts of the City of Rome, as well as representatives from the academic and research sectors. They reported the need to adjust the tone and scope of the factsheets to resonate with local contexts and initiated a more tailored, co-creative approach to advocacy with relevant stakeholders in Rome and surrounding areas.

- At EU level and in France, the European Science Foundation (ESF) promoted ACCTING through high-visibility moments. They organised a dedicated webinar during the EU Green Week and used their institutional events, such as their anniversary celebration, to feature ACCTING in a poster exhibition and reach audiences in research policy. At regional level they actively engaged with members of “*Start-up de Territoire*”, a dynamic initiative fostering local innovation and citizen-driven entrepreneurship. They also pursued media outreach and mapped major European platforms to ensure long-term visibility of ACCTING’s outputs.
- In Norway and Denmark, NTNU’s strategy centred on policy-relevant engagement. They hosted an online workshop on community energy and inclusive practices, invited a wide range of stakeholders including municipalities and private sector actors, and focused on fostering long-term collaborations. Their advocacy activities also included structured outreach to policymakers and corporate actors around Research Line 3.
- UAIC in Romania actively pursued advocacy with local authorities and the private sector. They promoted sustainable and seasonal food access by engaging municipal departments responsible for social services and public food provision. Additionally, they initiated dialogue with universities and the local chamber of commerce to encourage adoption of environmentally friendly food practices and employer engagement with inclusive sustainability.
- IGOT in Portugal focused on developing localised events to present ACCTING findings to Lisbon and Cascais municipalities. While early email campaigns yielded limited response, face-to-face engagement proved more promising. They began planning a dedicated Portuguese-language webinar and received an invitation to present ACCTING to visiting American students via the Luso-American Foundation, extending the project’s academic reach.
- ZSI and ECSA tailored their advocacy to citizen science and biodiversity. ZSI coordinated a media interview in Bulgaria and sought to amplify biodiversity-related recommendations across Balkan networks, particularly by engaging with citizen-driven initiatives. ECSA, while starting later, developed a focused strategy to connect with local actors in Hungary, promoting factsheets related to civil society and sustainable food systems.

Figure 7: Promotion of ACCTING at ESF’s 50th anniversary event

- Yellow Window coordinated targeted outreach across Belgium, Greece, and Cyprus. In Greece, early efforts to disseminate factsheets via email met with limited response; however, follow-up actions led to promising developments. Several municipalities including Thessaloniki, Themi, Kalamaria, and Athens expressed interest and requested meetings to explore ACCTING's findings in more depth. In Cyprus, factsheets were shared with local authorities. In Belgium, advocacy efforts culminated in the organisation of the seminar "Veilig Onderweg" (Safe in Transit), held on 6 May 2025 in Antwerp. The event gathered public transport operators, civil society representatives, and experts from the Flanders and Brussels regions to discuss the pressing issue of safety in public transport systems. Organised under the ACCTING project umbrella, the seminar centred on aggression, sexual intimidation, and strategies for prevention. The Towards Safer Mobility factsheet was used as an entry point for policy reflection and discussion. Operators from De Lijn, STIB-MIVB, and NMBS-SNCB shared current approaches and challenges, while a dynamic panel debate underlined that public transport safety is not merely an operational concern, but a deeply societal one. Key takeaways included the need for cross-sector collaboration, improved reporting mechanisms and multi-dimensional prevention strategies. The seminar also highlighted the relevance of frameworks like the UniSAFE 7P model for informing integrated policy responses. This event exemplified how ACCTING's recommendations can be activated in national advocacy dialogues and used to foster multisectoral cooperation.
- In Sweden, ORU and UGOT took a collaborative approach, coordinating their outreach to municipal actors and identifying key multipliers. The factsheets deemed most likely to have an impact in the Swedish context were [translated](#) and disseminated to relevant stakeholders. They recognised the need to go beyond dissemination and began planning magazine articles and seminar interventions to link factsheet content with policy debates in food, health, and local governance.

In sum, the consortium's advocacy approach has evolved from a dissemination-heavy model to a multifaceted and relational engagement strategy, rooted in contextual understanding, co-ownership, and sustained dialogue. While initial methods such as emailing factsheets to specific targets had limited traction, partners quickly pivoted toward more dynamic and locally tailored interventions. These included direct engagement with policymakers, the contextualisation and translation of factsheets into national languages and the organisation of workshops and info sessions designed to present recommendations in ways relevant to specific regional needs (e.g. IGOT in Lisbon, SU with İzmir Municipality). Several partners engaged municipal representatives, NGOs, and policymakers in structured dialogues, such as SEERC's outreach to agrotech clusters and local governments in Greece, or NTNU's facilitation of cross-country exchange on energy communities between Norway and Denmark.

Advocacy efforts also extended into public-facing activities, including radio programmes (SU), blog posts and magazine articles (ORU, SU), and seminars (YW in Belgium, ESF in France). ACCTING messages were disseminated through high-visibility events, such as ICLEI's contributions to the European Urban Resilience Forum and ESF's Green Week webinar. Partners also took part in external committees and advisory boards, as in ORU's participation in Uppsala's local food governance initiative and worked to co-create inclusive practices with NGOs and academic partners, including collaborations with forestry and environmental associations in Turkey.

Importantly, several actions directly encouraged uptake of ACCTING recommendations: from supporting municipalities in hosting local farmers' markets, to urging universities to provide healthier food options and engaging business chambers to develop local alliances for environmental goals. IGOT, for example, introduced project insights to international students, expanding awareness beyond policy circles.

This diverse mix of actions demonstrates that ACCTING advocacy is not only about policy influence, but also about relationship-building, public education, and catalysing inclusive transition efforts on the ground. While efforts are still ongoing and concrete figures (e.g. number of stakeholders reached, materials disseminated, events hosted) will be reported in the final technical report, the progress achieved so far illustrates the depth and breadth of ACCTING's policy engagement.

Info Sessions

To support the advocacy efforts, the ACCTING consortium was tasked with organising info sessions to present the project, its goals, and its results. Partners were free to choose the focus on the sessions (i.e. specific RL or outputs) and adapt to their local contexts (i.e. session format and language).

The sessions organised took various formats, including webinars (SEERC, ICLEI), digital lectures (ORU/UGOT), stakeholder workshops and meetings (ORU, ESF, NTNU, IGOT) and online info sessions (SU). Out of 17 info sessions organised, 7 took place online and 13 were held in the national language, aligning with the flexible implementation foreseen in the GA.

Table 2: Overview of Info Sessions

Partner	Date	Event title	Venue/place
SU	26-May-22	Disasters, Biodiversity and Gender in the Context of Green Deal ("Yeşil Mutabakat Bağlamında Afetler, Biyoçeşitlilik ve Toplumsal Cinsiyet")	Online
SU	25-May-22	Food, Gender and Vulnerable Groups in the Context of Green Deal ("Yeşil Mutabakat Bağlamında Gıda, Toplumsal Cinsiyet ve Kırılgan(laştırılmış) Gruplar")	Online
ORU	19-Nov-24	Rörelsenätverket Generation Pep: online presentation	Online, Örebro region
ESF	14-Nov-24, Dec 2024	Project presentation; workshop with "Start-Up de Territoires"	Strasbourg
ORU/UGOT	6-Mar-25	Cykling i socialt marginaliserade områden	Online
ORU/UGOT	27-Mar-25	Strong SSH webinar	Online
ORU/UGOT	04-Apr-25	ACCTING meets Stadsmissionen (webinar)	Online
ORU/UGOT	07-Apr-25	ACCTING webinar with network of stakeholders in the Örebro region	Online
UAIC	19-Oct-23	Implementing research projects: from idea to action.	UAIC, Iasi, Romania

ICLEI	17-Jan-24	Marginalized communities' access to healthy and sustainable food: Stories from Thessaloniki (<i>detailed in latter section</i>)	Online
UAIC	21-Feb-25	ACCTING results RC2	UAIC, Iasi, Romania
ORU	10-Apr-25	Swedish gender Equality Agency, gender equality board of researchers	Swedish gender equality agency
ORU	08-May-25	Cycling initiative, practice	Cycling initiative organisation Armkraft
YW	06-May-25	Veilig Onderweg	YW, Antwerp
K&I	09-Jan-25	Meeting with Solidarity Energy Communities Rome, Italy	Circolo SI Testaccio, Rome, Italy
IGOT	24-Mar-25	Food Inclusion: Access to Healthy and Sustainable Food for Vulnerable Groups [in Portuguese]	TTC@ULisboa — Technology Transfer and Knowledge Enhancement Centre of the Universidade de Lisboa

Target: 12 info sessions on the project

Achieved: 15 info sessions on the project

Presentations at events targeting civil society

In addition to the above-mentioned advocacy efforts and participation at events targeting the scientific community as presented in the Knowledge Dissemination section, the following presentations primarily aimed to promote the project's factsheets to civil society organisations and policymakers.

- Botha, D (2024). Citizens Participation as an essential element to face climate challenges [Presentation]. ALDA General Assembly, Barcelona, Spain.
- Denis, A, Niethammer, J, Tzamouranou, E (2024). "Co-creating inclusive climate adaptation solutions: an interactive workshop on citizen engagement" [workshop]. European Urban Resilience Forum EURESFO, Valencia, Spain
- Balkmar, D (2024) "I Sverige cyklar man och dricker vatten": föreställningar om cykling och vardagscyklings tyngder och avlastningar. National cycling conference, Örebro, Sweden.
- Strid, S., Niethammer, J. (2024). Better together: Local governments and communities collaborating for just, resilient cities [workshop]. 10th European Conference on Sustainable Cities and Towns 2024, Aalborg, Denmark.

- Denis, A. (2025), Participation at round table of “Femmes en mouvement”, an association of 50+ legal entities active in public transport in France on “Sécurité des femmes dans les transports: l’impact de la gouvernance”. Paris, France.

Webinars promoting the factsheets

To support the uptake of ACCTING’s policy recommendations by relevant stakeholders, a series of webinars was organised as part of the project’s advocacy strategy. These online sessions served to translate key findings from the research into accessible knowledge for civil society actors, local authorities, and practitioners. Each webinar focused on a specific theme aligned with the operational recommendations developed within the project and aimed to foster exchange between researchers, activists, and local leaders. The webinars offered both conceptual framing and concrete case-based reflections, contributing to the broader dissemination goals.

Two webinars were organised at the end of the first cycle:

- The **first webinar**, [“Marginalised communities’ access to healthy and sustainable food: Stories from Thessaloniki”](#) was co-organised with Urban Community and took place on **17 January 2024**. It focused on how local initiatives and community-based models can improve food access for vulnerable groups in urban areas. ACCTING researchers opened the session by presenting policy recommendations on equitable access to healthy and sustainable food systems. This was followed by a compelling intervention from Greek activist **Filippos Polatsidis**, representing *Pervolarides of Thessaloniki*, a solidarity-based collective distributing seasonal and regional food to those in need. He reflected on the organisation’s hands-on experience and the structural barriers encountered in practice, underscoring the need for food policy reform at local and national levels. The event concluded with an open dialogue, where participants shared experiences from their local contexts and collectively discussed ways to scale inclusive food distribution models.
- The second webinar, titled [“Rooted in Equality: Strengthening Food Security through Gender+ Inclusive and Sustainable Small-Scale Farming”](#), took place on **25 April 2024**, and was based on the ACCTING factsheet “Local is Beautiful: gender+ inclusive agricultural policies and civil society practices for and with small farmers”. The session began with **Ayşe Gül Altınay** (Sabancı University), who provided an overview of the research insights and introduced the key recommendations for supporting small-scale farmers through gender+ inclusive policy frameworks. She was joined by **Aylin Topal**, Associate Professor at Middle East Technical University, who brought in a political ecology lens to critically analyse dominant agricultural policy paradigms. **Martin Felix Gajdusek**, researcher at ZSI, contributed insights from comparative fieldwork and pilot actions. Together, the speakers engaged in a rich discussion on the need to realign European Green Deal strategies with grassroots ecofeminist priorities, reinforcing the message that food justice must be both socially and ecologically sustainable.

These two webinars laid the groundwork for a broader series of thematic advocacy events described above. In total, **five additional webinars were organised after the second research cycle**, exceeding the initial plan of two and further amplifying the project’s policy impact across multiple domains including mobility, participatory governance, wellbeing, climate resilience and resistance movements. These events brought together policymakers, practitioners, researchers, and civil society actors to discuss how inclusive policies can be shaped and implemented in practice, and to promote the uptake of ACCTING’s operational recommendations and factsheets. Each webinar was designed

to align closely with the project's priority themes and the factsheets, focusing on different dimensions of vulnerability and structural inequality exacerbated by Green Deal policies.

1. The **first webinar**, titled “[Towards Safer Mobility: Addressing Violence in Public Transportation](#)”, took place on **24 April 2025**. The session explored the gendered and intersectional barriers that limit safe access to transport for women and marginalised communities, a challenge often overlooked in transport policy. Framed around the findings of the ACCTING factsheet “[Towards Safer Mobility: A Holistic Approach to Tackling Violence in Public Transportation](#)”, the session aimed to raise awareness and promote evidence-based strategies to ensure safety as a prerequisite for an inclusive green transition. Opening the discussion, **Sara Ortiz Escalante** from Col·lectiu Punt 6 drew on years of feminist urban research and participatory mapping to underscore how the design of transport systems often ignores the everyday safety concerns of women and LGBTQI+ individuals. She highlighted how policies based solely on infrastructure fail to address the lived experiences of fear and exclusion. **Jan Politiek**, Security Expert at the UITP EU Department, added perspectives from the transport sector, addressing the role of safety protocols, training and institutional commitment to preventing and responding to harassment and violence. Together, the speakers reflected on the role of partnerships between urban planners, transport authorities, civil society and researchers, drawing connections to the [UniSAFE 7P model](#), particularly around prevention, protection, and participation. The webinar also featured “better stories” from across Europe, illustrating how small-scale interventions such as safe reporting systems or gender-sensitive design can make a significant impact on both users’ and workers’ experiences of safety. The session attracted participants from across policy, urban planning, transport operations and NGOs, and provided a platform to reinforce the message that addressing safety in mobility is not an add-on but a central condition for equity and inclusion in green transition efforts.
2. The webinar “[Collaborative Governance for Just Urban Transitions: How to Build Public–Civil Society Partnerships?](#)” was held on **13 May 2025**. It addressed the critical need for more inclusive and cooperative governance models in urban sustainability efforts. Around Europe, local governments and community-led initiatives are increasingly driving change aligned with local priorities, yet both actors often lack the capacity to tackle complex sustainability challenges independently. This webinar explored how strategic partnerships between public authorities and civil society organisations (CSOs) can bridge that gap to deliver socially just and climate-resilient transitions at the local level. **Daniel Botha**, Expert in Justice Equity & Democracy at ICLEI Europe and consortium member, framed the webinar with key insights and gaps on collaborative governance drawn from the ACCTING pilot actions. **Nikos Zaharis**, Director of SEERC and ACCTING consortium member, opened the discussion by sharing the key recommendations of the factsheet “Public civil society partnerships for behavioural change”. He emphasised the importance of trust, mutual accountability, and long-term commitment in building effective partnerships. **Sophia Silverton**, Expert in the Justice, Equity and Democracy team at ICLEI Europe, contributed insights from her experience working on the Urban Community and COM4LGD projects, where local governments and grassroots actors co-designed urban policies through participatory processes. She illustrated how such collaborations can help institutional actors tap into community knowledge and improve both legitimacy and impact. The session offered practical guidance on how to initiate, structure, and sustain public–civil society collaboration in climate governance and was particularly relevant for local policymakers, urban planners and CSOs engaged in local sustainability and

climate justice. It reinforced the ACCTING advocacy message that inclusive transitions require institutional openness to community-led innovation and ongoing cooperation across sectors.

3. The webinar “[Women, Villages, Forests: Local Struggle and Solidarity Experiences from Greece and Türkiye](#)” was held **on 15 May 2025** and conducted in both Greek and Turkish, with simultaneous interpretation. It brought together village leaders, shepherds, farmers, firefighters and grassroots organisers predominantly women from rural areas on both sides of the Aegean, to share knowledge, struggles and community-led responses to the rising threat of forest fires. The event opened with a presentation of ACCTING’s policy recommendations titled “Valuing Indigenous and Local Knowledge in Disaster Management and Nature Protection” followed by the introduction of a practical toolkit “Reducing Forest Fire Risk for Local Communities” developed by DOCK – Social Solidarity in the Economic Sector, as part of an ACCTING-supported pilots in Greece. The discussion was moderated by Esin Düzel (Sabancı University), who wove together stories of resilience, community wisdom and cross-border solidarity. Speakers included Şerife Güzel (Izmir Municipality), Nejla Işık (Ikizköy Village, Türkiye), Sevil Duman (Urla Birgi Village, Türkiye) and Pervin Savran (Sarikeçililer Life and Solidarity Association), alongside Ilias Anagnostopoulos (Manganiako Village, Greece), Danae Athanassopoulou (Ancient Messene Cultural Association), Dimitra Papaioannidou (Ecomuseum Zagori), and Panagiotis Giannakopoulos and Elena Tzamouranou (Villages in Action – Community Based Institute). These participants shared powerful insights on the ancestral knowledge held by local communities and the everyday leadership exercised by women in protecting ecosystems, preparing for disasters and caring for their villages and forests. Ayşe Gül Altınay (EarthSky Solidarity Association) delivered the concluding remarks, framing the gathering as a historic moment of “re-membering and re-gathering” the ancient, often fragmented planetary wisdom shared across the Aegean. Her reflections acknowledged the cross-border nature of both ecological threats and human solidarity, invoking the idea that “the Aegean belongs to the fish” as a symbol of ecological interdependence and peace. This webinar embodied the core purpose of ACCTING’s advocacy work bringing forward local knowledge, amplifying grassroots leadership and building bridges between communities and policymakers to shape inclusive environmental governance. It was recorded and made available with English subtitles to ensure wider accessibility across the ACCTING network and beyond.
4. The webinar “[Wellbeing as a Driver for Sustainable Behavioural Change](#)” took place **on 16 May 2025** and explored how wellbeing-centred approaches can foster long-term behavioural change in support of environmental and social objectives. Drawing on ACCTING research and case studies from across Europe, the session made the case for reframing sustainability not only through environmental urgency but also through everyday experiences of care, connection and community. **Prof. Dilay Celebi Gonidis**, Senior Researcher at SEERC and member of the ACCTING team, opened the session by presenting the project’s factsheet “Wellbeing as a Trigger for Behavioural Change”. Her presentation highlighted how wellbeing can serve as both a motivation and outcome of sustainable practices, with implications for education, mobility, food systems and urban policy. **Aart Kerremans**, Consultant at Yellow Window, also introduced findings from ACCTING’s research and pilot projects, illustrating how wellbeing-oriented frameworks can promote inclusive behavioural shifts. Reacting to the presentations, **Elina Moraitopoulou**, Scientific Coordinator of Mamagea, an environmental organisation based in Thessaloniki, shared insights from the Food4Schools initiative an education-based, participatory project that works to bring healthy and sustainable food into schools. Her response provided a grounded example of how young

people and educators can co-create supportive food environments that foster ecological awareness and social cohesion. Bringing together educators, civil society actors, and urban policy stakeholders, the session underscored the importance of designing interventions that centre wellbeing as a pathway toward more just and effective sustainability transitions.

5. The final webinar titled “[Transformative Resistance: Engaging Marginalised Groups for a Just Green Transition](#)”, took place on **20 May 2025**. It focused on resistance as a form of agency and transformation, highlighting how marginalised communities actively shape the green transition through everyday practices of resilience, dissent and innovation. Rather than treating resistance as opposition to policy, the session positioned it as a critical and generative force for justice-oriented climate action. Drawing from ACCTING’s research and case studies from Turkey, Hungary and Italy, the webinar examined how bottom-up mobilisation challenges dominant narratives and creates alternative visions for sustainability. The session began with **Esin Düzel** (Sabancı University), who introduced and presented the ACCTING factsheet “Transformative Resistance: Policy Insights from Marginalised Communities”. She contextualised the factsheet’s findings within broader debates on equity and participatory governance in environmental policy. **Dr Ana Maria Vargas Falla**, a scholar of inclusive governance and civic participation, opened the discussion by unpacking the political potential of resistance in climate transitions. She emphasised the need to move beyond technocratic approaches and to centre the lived experiences of those most affected by environmental injustices. **Dr Hikmet Batuhan Günşen**, drawing from his research in post-migrant and Roma communities, shared examples of how grassroots organising can disrupt extractivist logics and reframe local development priorities. Together, the speakers provided both theoretical insights and empirical evidence on how resistance can be integrated into inclusive policy design. The session was particularly relevant for policymakers, grassroots movements, environmental justice advocates, and researchers working on equitable climate governance.

All webinars are promoted among the project and partners’ network, drawing upon the stakeholder database mentioned above and using the following dissemination channels:

- Articles on project website, shared on relevant blogs
- Social media
- Project and partners’ newsletters
- Direct emails

In this respect, ICLEI, ECSA, and ESF played a particular role in disseminating the project results among their network of stakeholders, working groups respectively involved in urban local development, citizen science, and overall research, and in inviting them to participate in the webinars.

All webinars are recorded and available as replay on the project [YouTube channel](#) and on the project website.

Table 3: Overview of webinars promoting the factsheets

#	Webinar	Date	No of participants	YouTube views
1	Marginalised communities’ access to healthy and sustainable food: Stories from Thessaloniki	17 January 2024	37	86
2	Rooted in Equality: Strengthening Food Security	25 April 2024	36	70

	through Gender+ Inclusive and Sustainable Small-Scale Farming			
3	Towards safer mobility: addressing violence in public transportation	24 April 2025	24	25
4	Collaborative governance for just urban transitions: How to build public-civil society partnerships?	13 May 2025	17	36
5	Women, Villages, Forests: Local Struggle and Solidarity Experiences from Greece and Türkiye	15 May 2025	136	147
6	Wellbeing as a driver for sustainable behavioural change	16 May 2025	15	21
7	Transformative Resistance: Engaging marginalised groups for a just green transition	20 May 2025	18	24
Total number			283	409

Target: 4 webinars towards civil society with a total of 200 participants

Reach: 7 webinars towards civil society with a total of 283 participants

Final conference

On 29 April 2025, ACCTING held its Final Conference titled “**Empowering Change: Building a Fair and Inclusive Green Deal**” to present research insights, their demonstration through pilot actions, and project outputs, in discussion with external experts. The conference opened with a keynote address, setting the stage for three thematic sessions that will present ACCTING’s **research findings**, **innovations**, and **proposed actions** for a fairer Green Deal. These sessions addressed key challenges, showcased pioneering solutions, fostering cross-sector collaboration to ensure that the benefits of the Green Deal are equitably distributed across all segments of society.

- Keynote speech: [“Redefining the Public Interest”](#) by Tunç Soyer, Politician and lawyer, former mayor of Ismir.
- Session 1: [Learning from the grassroots: Engaging with marginalised groups to co-create a just transition](#). Moderated by Ayşe Gül Altınay, consortium partners Marina Cacace (K&I), Lina Sandström (UGOT) and Esin Düzel, (SU) presented results from ACCTING, in discussion with Lara Houston, Anglia Ruskin University, and Helen Cole, Autonomous University of Barcelona.
- Session 2: [From innovation to impact: Leveraging commons for a just transition](#). Moderated by Jannis Niethammer (ICLEI), the panel featured ACCTING’s results presented by Burcu Borhan Türeli (SU), a pilot project presented by Dimitra Papaioannidou, EcoMuseum Zagori, and experience from the Commons Network in the Netherlands, by Sophie Bloemen.

- Session 3: [Advancing behavioural change through partnerships and collaboration](#). Moderated by Nikos Zaharis, the panel discussed the topic from the point of view of a diverse range of stakeholders, with researcher Gabriele Quinti (K&I), presenting ACCTING's related project's recommendations, followed by Esteban Pelayo, Alicante Science Park, representing the business sector, Laura Kaestele, ECOLISE, an NGO, and Edoardo Zanchini, from the City of Rome.
- [Concluding statements](#) by Sofia Strid, UGOT
- A poster presentation highlighted the work from projects and initiatives working on inclusivity, sustainability, and the inclusion of vulnerable groups, as well as the outputs of the pilot projects.

The event took place in La Tricoterie in Brussels and was recorded, with replays available on the project's [YouTube channel](#) on a dedicated playlist. At the time of the publication of this deliverable, the replays have collected 330 views overall.

In terms of participation, the conference gathered a diverse group of stakeholders, including civil society actors, NGOs, researchers, policymakers including representatives of the European Commission (DG EMPL) and the City of Rome, pilot project representatives, and community leaders. Despite all odds - a power outage in Spain the previous day and a national strike in Belgium on the same day impacting all public transportation - the event gathered 77 attendees in person out of 125 registrations.

To promote the event and gain the attention of media and policymakers, several communication activities were carried out:

- Targeted emails: template invitation emails were provided for consortium members to send personal invitations, favouring already established connections. Emails were sent to members of the ACCTING network, experts and activists involved in the project activities, and policymakers among others.
- Newsletter campaign: the final conference was first announced via a "save the date" in the December 2024 newsletter, followed by two issues in March and April 2025 which explored the programme and invited speakers.
- Social media promotion: a series of posts were published across LinkedIn, and Facebook highlighting speakers, specific sessions and key themes covered in the programme. Speaker institutions and related projects were regularly tagged to boost visibility.
- Platforms: the conference was published as an event on Linked, Facebook, EUAgenda and Eventbrite.

Communication activities during and after the event:

- Attendees were invited to share their key highlights and takeaways on dedicated posters during the event.
- Posts were shared on LinkedIn before and after the event using key quotes, speaker highlights, and pictures of the day.
- A [blog post](#) was published in the project news section to promote the replays and the [event page on the ACCTING website](#) was updated to centralise replays and programme information, accessible to those who could not attend live.

- A newsletter was released in early May summarising the event and promoting the availability of session replays.

On 29 April 2025 the ACCTING project held its Final Conference in Brussels, bringing together researchers, policymakers, civil society leaders and community voices for a day of rich discussions and shared learning. With just one month to go before the project's conclusion, the event marked a key moment to reflect on ACCTING's contribution to building a fair and inclusive European Green Deal. A huge thank you to all speakers, pilot project representatives, poster presenters, and every attendee who contributed to the day's meaningful conversations.

Target: 240 participants (physical and virtual)

Achieved: 77 participants in person, up to 83 replays of a session to date

Promotion of the research agenda

The two research agendas developed at the end of each cycle and summarised in D5.3 and D5.5 aim to bridge critical knowledge gaps at the intersection of Green Deal policy implementation, behavioural change, and inequality, with specific attention to how such changes affect vulnerable groups across Europe. Efforts were devoted to encouraging their uptake by the research community, and particularly research funding organisations (RFOs), and to stimulate further inclusive, equity-oriented research.

The agendas were published on the [open-access Zenodo community](#), featured [on the project website](#), and promoted through ACCTING's communication channels. As foreseen, two webinars were planned per research cycle. However, the consortium exceeded this target, organising **five webinars** overall one in the first reporting period and four in the second to increase outreach and thematic depth. These webinars were designed to present the agendas' key findings and to foster dialogue between researchers, RFOs, and other stakeholders.

Researchers and RFOs at various levels were actively encouraged to engage with the ACCTING research agendas and participate in the dedicated webinars for further discussion and knowledge exchange. To reach a broad and diverse audience of RFOs, consortium members undertook targeted outreach through their individual networks. At the European level, umbrella organisations such as Science Europe were contacted to facilitate wider dissemination, while regional-level RFOs were

approached through established synergies with the [GENDERACTIONplus](#) project, which brings together funders committed to integrating gender equality into research funding mechanisms. Communication efforts were also supported by the project's dissemination channels and further amplified through the networks of sister projects.

1. The first webinar, "[Bridging the Gap: Inclusive Criteria for NGO Funding](#)", held on **1 October 2024**, focused on the role of inclusivity in funding practices. Moderated by **Nikos Zaharis** (SEERC), the session brought together perspectives from NGOs and funders on how calls and funding schemes can better respond to the needs of vulnerable groups. **Dr. Sotiris Petropoulos**, Associate Professor at the University of the Peloponnese and co-founder of HIGGS, discussed strategies NGOs can use to highlight social inclusion in proposals. **Prof. Andrei Holman**, psychologist and research evaluator at Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași, reflected on how inclusivity criteria can be better embedded in funding evaluation processes. This webinar did not focus directly on a specific part of the research agenda of the first research cycle. It laid essential groundwork to attract attention to the research agenda by highlighting the systemic barriers that hinder inclusive research.
2. The next event held during the second research cycle followed a similar approach, to attract the target group without choosing to promote a limited part of the research agenda. The webinar "**Funding Support for Bottom-Up Initiatives: An Overview of Sources & Tips for Applying**", was organised in collaboration with the Urban Community for Sustainable and Just Cities (ICLEI). Held as part of ACCTING's Community Conversation series in early 2025, the webinar responded to a recurring challenge highlighted across the project's research and pilot actions: the persistent funding bottlenecks faced by grassroots and community-led sustainability initiatives. The session brought together a diverse audience of civil society organisations, RFOs and local actors engaged in inclusive environmental transformation. Expert insights were offered by Matthew Bach (ICLEI Europe), Janelle Conn (ECOLISE), and Ania Rok (independent expert on climate and philanthropy), each bringing distinct perspectives on navigating the European funding landscape. The conversation explored the structural obstacles that hinder bottom-up participation in funding programmes and offered concrete strategies to improve access ranging from building coalitions and clarifying eligibility criteria, to leveraging philanthropy and alternative financing. The discussion was grounded in ACCTING's wider advocacy objective of amplifying the role of community actors in delivering socially just transitions. This webinar reaffirmed that funding mechanisms must be designed with the realities of grassroots organisations in mind if the European Green Deal is to be inclusive and effective. It also served to disseminate ACCTING's operational recommendations calling for increased accessibility, transparency, and support for locally rooted action. Although not originally planned as a webinar promoting the research agenda per se, the "Funding Support for Bottom-Up Initiatives" webinar aligns with the overarching objective of ACCTING to stimulate further research and inclusive knowledge production. By addressing the funding challenges faced by community-based actors and offering practical guidance for accessing support mechanisms, the webinar contributed to ACCTING's ambition to bridge research and action. It created synergies between research insights on structural inequalities and the operational realities of local initiatives, supporting the broader uptake of inclusive agendas by equipping actors with the resources needed to engage in socially just transition efforts.
3. After the research agenda based on the second cycle research became available, a series of three webinars was launched under the overarching title "Addressing Knowledge Gaps for a More Inclusive Green Deal" to promote the research agenda. This was challenging given the short period between the availability of the research agenda and the end of the project. All webinars took place

in May 2025. The first in this series of three research agenda webinars, “[Advancing Social Science Research for a Just Green Transition](#)”, was held on **8 May 2025**. This session introduced key knowledge gaps identified in the ACCTING Research Agendas and focused specifically on how future research can address social inequalities, inclusion and intersectionality within the context of climate and environmental transitions. The agenda foregrounded two priority research domains: **inclusive energy communities**, with a focus on participation barriers and behavioural change dynamics, and **sustainable food systems**, especially the structural enablers and constraints of inclusivity within food movements. Two external speakers were invited to respond to the research agenda and provide insights from their own fields. **Rosie Day**, researcher at the School of Geography, Earth and Environmental Sciences at the University of Birmingham, reflected on the role of social sciences in energy justice research, underlining the need to consider power relations and embedded inequalities in community energy systems. **Cecília Delgado**, co-founder and President of Alimentar Cidades Sustentáveis, drew from her work on participatory urban food governance to discuss how food movements can act as spaces of democratic innovation and environmental transformation. Both speakers validated the relevance of the proposed research questions while encouraging deeper engagement with marginalised voices in future studies.

4. The second webinar in the series “[Research Supporting Social Impact – Sustainability through Innovation](#)” was held on **19 May 2025**. The event focused on the intersection of inclusive environmental research and socially transformative innovation, with particular emphasis on the role of sustainable food systems. The session opened with an introduction by Vasia Madesi (Yellow Window), who contextualised the webinar within the second ACCTING Research Agenda and its aim to bridge knowledge gaps on behaviour, equity and the Green Deal. **Patricia Abrantes** from IGOT presented the agenda's thematic focus on inclusive and sustainable food systems, highlighting key research questions such as how bottom-up initiatives can drive behavioural change in consumption patterns and what structural enablers or barriers influence their success. As an external respondent, **Dimitra Papaioannidou**, Project Manager at the Ecomuseum Zagori and expert in regenerative development, offered a practice-based perspective on these themes. Drawing from her work in biodiversity conservation and environmental education, she stressed the need for locally grounded, community-led research that connects ecological sustainability with cultural heritage and livelihoods. The session concluded with moderated questions and answers, creating space for researchers, civil society actors, and RFOs to exchange ideas and explore future research directions. The webinar reinforced the ACCTING agenda's relevance for shaping inclusive and impactful environmental research frameworks.
5. The third and final webinar in the ACCTING series dedicated to the promotion of the research agenda was held on **22 May 2025** under the title [More Inclusive Sustainability Policies](#). This session focused on how future research can shape the design and implementation of inclusive policy frameworks in support of Green Deal objectives. Drawing on ACCTING's research agendas, the webinar addressed key knowledge gaps related to institutional frameworks and the (co-)design of sustainability policies, particularly in the context of inclusive and sustainable mobility. The session was introduced by Dag Balkmar, Associate Professor and Senior Lecturer in Gender Studies at Örebro University, who framed the discussion around his research on transport poverty, mobility justice, and intersectional approaches to sustainable mobility. Francesca Pugliese, researcher at K&I and member of the ACCTING consortium, elaborated on the social and institutional dynamics that influence whether local authorities adopt co-creative, inclusive approaches when designing mobility policies. Their contributions highlighted the importance of understanding not only the content of policies but also the structural and cultural factors that shape how they are created and for whom. Reacting to the research agenda, Hélène Bouscasse,

Research Fellow at INRAE, brought an external perspective grounded in spatial and transport economics. She offered reflections on behavioural modelling, mobility-related health impacts, and the interdisciplinary intersections between climate research, social science, and infrastructure planning. Her insights helped underline the necessity of embedding gender+, spatial justice, and inclusivity considerations into ongoing and future research efforts. The webinar was particularly relevant for researchers, civil society actors, and funding organisations committed to supporting intersectional, inclusive sustainability transitions. It concluded the research agenda promotion series by reinforcing ACCTING’s core message: inclusive policies require inclusive knowledge production processes.

Table 4: Overview of webinars promoting the research agenda

#	Webinar	Date	No participants	YouTube views
1	Bridging the Gap: Inclusive Criteria for NGO Funding	1 October 2024	42	94
2	Funding Support for Bottom-Up Initiatives: An Overview of Sources & Tips for Applying	11 February 2025	24	Not applicable
3	Advancing Social Science Research for a Just Green Transition	8 May 2025	18	14
4	Research Supporting Social Impact – Sustainability through Innovation	19 May 2025	8	23
5	More Inclusive Sustainability Policies	22 May 2025	12	18
Total number			104	149

Target: 4 webinars for RFOs with a total of 100 participants

Achieved: 5 webinars for RFOs with a total of 104 participants

Communication activities and channels

Communication activities focused on triggering interest in the project's scope and activities and thus raising awareness on the impacts of Green Deal policies on vulnerable groups. They also supported the dissemination of the project's outputs.

The Project Communication Toolkit (D7.2) was submitted in M4 as a base to promote the project's cause, objectives, and outputs over the project lifetime. It described in detail the various online tools used to promote the project, namely the project website, social media channels, newsletters, and press releases. Offline tools included a brochure, roll-up, project presentation slides, posters.

ACCTING Website

Website development

The project website was the backbone of the project communication activities, providing public and specific target groups with a single entry for all information related to the project. The website was regularly updated with recent and relevant project information. Information on the project's objectives and results was widely disseminated also in web campaigns as to have maximum sectoral and cross-sectoral impact.

A temporary landing page was set up to provide basic project information from M1 and the finalised website was launched in early June 2022.

The website describes the project, its consortium, related projects, the challenges of behavioural change for the Green Deal, and the research lines. It offers regular news, the outputs developed by the project and a media kit, and includes a registration form to join the ACCTING Network. Access to the website and the continuously updated information, with at least one blog post each month, is ensured by ESF, with operational support from ICLEI during the first research cycle.

Its design takes into consideration the needs of visual impaired users, for an inclusive approach.

During the project lifetime, the number of unique website visitors has reached **19K**, with an average engagement time of 1m11s.

ACCTING website address: <https://accting.eu>

Also redirected from <https://accting-project.eu>

Figure 4: ACCTING website homepage

Targets: 5000 unique visitors

Achieved: 11K unique visitors

Blog entries

Blog entries provided regular updates on the project's progress and results, as well as posts related to behavioural change for the Green Deal, aiming to enhance awareness, interest, and engagement. Partners were invited to contribute to raising awareness about the project's research issues by providing content for at least one blog article per year during the project.

During the first cycle, blog posts focused on introducing the foundations of the project, i.e. ACCTING's eight research lines and defining key concepts. Later, the focus shifted to concrete outputs, including pilot projects, factsheets, and research agendas. Another important focus of blog posts was the promotion of events, with webinars regularly posted on the website. All posts were featured on the project homepage and shared on social media with dedicated visuals.

In total, 44 blog posts were published during the project lifetime (excluding inspiring initiatives, case studies and individual narratives).

Target: 36 blog entries

Achieved: 44 blog entries

Figure 8: ACCTING blog posts on the project website:

Partners' websites

Partners were also requested to make reference to the project on their own website, and regularly share the project's outputs in their news sections.

Figure 6: Presentation of ACCTING on partners' websites

Activity on social media

Social media activities were expected to contribute significantly to raising awareness about the impacts of Green Deal policies on vulnerable groups and promoting the project's activities and outputs to a wider audience of stakeholders. Partners were also encouraged to share the publications produced within the project on individual profiles on ResearchGate and Academia, with full acknowledgement to the ACCTING project.

Given its aims and stakeholders' profiles, ACCTING first focused on LinkedIn and X (Twitter) as main channels, commonly used by media, policymakers and the scientific community. At the beginning of 2025 and following a concertation with the consortium, it was decided to discontinue publications on the Twitter/X account and focus communication efforts on LinkedIn. This decision didn't impact the overall number of followers negatively as, at the end of the project, the ACCTING LinkedIn gathered 903 followers, nearly doubling in one year.

A Facebook profile was also created to share the call for pilot actions, as NGOs and smaller groups tend to favour this social network. The following social media accounts have been set up:

LinkedIn: [/company/accting](https://www.linkedin.com/company/accting)

Facebook: [accting](https://www.facebook.com/accting)

Twitter/X: [@ACCTING_EU](https://twitter.com/ACCTING_EU) (left open to redirect to the website)

Campaigns

All along the project lifetime, publications on these social media channels aimed not only at raising awareness about the impacts of Green Deal policies on vulnerable groups but also at promoting participation in project activities (call for pilot projects, participation in webinars and final conference, views of their replay) and the uptake of ACCTING factsheets, policy briefs, research agendas and other outputs.

Various social media campaigns were launched during the project timeline, starting with a presentation of consortium

Figure 9: Screenshot of ACCTING's account on X

partners, research lines and key terms used. Other campaigns ran more regularly, introducing ACCTING outputs (factsheets, research agendas, policy briefs) and pilot projects, as well as highlighting inspiring initiatives, individual narratives and case studies. Social media posts also aligned with relevant international days (i.e. European Mobility Week, World Food Day, World Environment Day) to amplify engagement around ACCTING's thematic areas.

Engagement strategies included posting on a regular basis, tagging influential individual and corporate channels, inviting connections to follow the page, using LinkedIn features (newsletter, events), hashtags (#EUGreenDeal, #GreenDeal, #JustTransition, #JustTransition4All, #ClimateJustice...), cross-posting about the channel on other platforms (website publications, emails...).

Figure 10: Post introducing the Factsheets

Figure 11: Publication promoting the webinar series

Figure 12: Publication leveraging the World Food Day

Analytics

To this date, the project gathers 901 followers on LinkedIn and 119 on Facebook. Just in its final year, the project published 150 posts on LinkedIn gathering 101,453 impressions and 1,543 reactions, demonstrating its active use and reach on the platform. Active reposting by consortium partners contributed to this high impact.

Figure 13: Number of impressions on ACCTING’s LinkedIn account from June 2024 to May 2025

Metrics

Figure 14: Number of clicks on ACCTING's LinkedIn publications, from June 2024 to May 2025

Metrics

Figure 15: Number of members reached on ACCTING's LinkedIn channel, from June 2024 to May 2025

Targets: 500 social media followers

Achieved: 900 followers on one social media channel

Reddit

Towards the end of the project, the use of reddit was tested to expand the project's reach to additional communities. Publications in communities such as r/resilientcommunities, r/ClimateActionPlan, led to a high number of views, but low engagement. Due to limited resources, publications on this channel were not prioritised.

Figure 16: Publication on reddit

Electronic project newsletter

Electronic newsletters were published three to four times a year, starting in M4. The newsletters contained specific information about project news, milestones, and outputs. They were disseminated to the ACCTING mailing list, reaching relevant stakeholder organisations as well as individuals. Subscribers can sign up to the newsletter [on the project website](#) or via specific posts on social media. The newsletters' content also regularly fed into partners' newsletters. Below are examples of topics that were covered across the 14 issues published:

- Launch of the project and first actions
- Download of project's outputs: insights, publications, recommendations, guidelines, presentations, tools, deliverables...
- Inspiring practices
- Upcoming events, such as conferences or workshops
- News from partner projects
- A request to follow the project on its social media channels

The newsletter was edited with the MailChimp platform. The subscription module complies to GDPR requirements. Subscribers give their consent to receive regular updates and are informed on their rights regarding their data.

During the project lifetime, 14 issues were sent to a total of 330 subscribers, with a wrap-up issue scheduled for June 2025. Each issue was then disseminated to a wider public audience through other communication channels (internal emails, social media, and links displayed on the project website).

- [Newsletter #1 – July 2022](#)
- [Newsletter #2 – October 2022](#)
- [Newsletter #3 – December 2022](#)
- [Newsletter #4 – March 2023](#)

- [Newsletter #5 – July 2023](#)
- [Newsletter #6 – October 2023](#)
- [Newsletter #7 – December 2023](#)
- [Newsletter #8 – February 2024](#)
- [Newsletter #9 – May 2024](#)
- [Newsletter #10 – September 2024](#)
- [Newsletter #11 – December 2024](#)
- [Newsletter #12 – March 2025](#)
- [Newsletter #13 – April 2025](#)
- [Newsletter #14 – May 2025](#)

Starting in 2024 a project newsletter was also issued through LinkedIn to improve its reach. Seven editions have been published on the social platform, gathering 327 subscribers on LinkedIn by the end of the project.

Target: 12 e-newsletters disseminated to subscribers and to the wider public audience

Achieved: 12 newsletters on Mailchimp, 7 on LinkedIn.

Press release

Five press releases were published during the project:

- [Launch of ACCTING, AdvanCing behavioural Change Through an Inclusive Green deal](#)
15 February 2022
- [How policymakers, employers and civil society organisations can reduce inequalities caused or worsened by the European Green Deal](#)
11 January 2024
- [Piloting ten innovative solutions for an inclusive European Green Deal](#)
22 January 2024
- [Insights and recommendations to reduce inequalities caused or worsened by the European Green Deal](#)
1 March 2025
- [ACCTING Final Conference: Empowering Change for a Fair and Inclusive Green Deal](#)
10 April 2025

Press releases are shared with ACCTING partners, published on [a dedicated section of the project website](#), and disseminated among targeted stakeholders (i.e. for the launch of pilot projects, pilot organisations were invited to share the dedicated press release among their own networks).

A sixth press releases is foreseen to be published in May to promote the project's final policy brief

Two event specific press releases were published by Yellow Window for the national event "Safely on the way: solutions for improved safety on public transport". This was in April 2025 and after the event of May 6 2025. Both press releases were shared through the Belga agency platform with 770+ press contacts.

Target: 8 press releases (4 by cycle) sent from 11 countries (partners)

Monitoring and evaluation of dissemination and communication activities

The Communication and Dissemination Strategy foresaw a set of concrete quantitative and qualitative Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to monitor the effectiveness of its implementation and measure whether the strategic objectives relating to the outreach of the project were being achieved. Hereafter is a final evaluation.

Indicator	Overall target	Status at M40
Scientific publications submitted	20	25
International conferences where ACCTING is presented	3	11
Website unique visitors	5000 visits	19k
Number of countries where website visits are from	50	169
Social media followers	500	1019
Twitter, and LinkedIn posts	200	525+
Newsletters	12	15
Press releases	8	7
Blog posts	36	44
Participants at webinars promoting the research agenda	100	104 participants, 149 replays
Participants at public webinars	200	283 participants, 409 replays
Participants at final conference	240 physical and virtual participants (120/120)	77 physical + 80 views on replay

Table 3: KPIs – Communication and Dissemination

The evaluation of communication activities was based on monitoring of the communication programme's efficiency in terms of output, such as readership, viewership statistics, attendance at events, inquiry or response rates, analysis of media coverage, and media monitoring, website statistics.

In order to achieve the above, we elaborated periodical monitoring reports that summarised results and highlight progress, advantages and shortcomings to allow timely suggestions for improvement.

Exploitation of results

This section describes the pathway to exploit ACCTING's results to maximise their impact within the ACCTING Network, as well as the broader European Research Area. To support and strengthen the exploitation strategy, ACCTING has been working with the **Horizon Booster** services. Through this collaboration, the project has benefited from tailored guidance on identifying Key Exploitable Results (KERs), refining its value proposition, and planning sustainable pathways for uptake. The Readiness Assessment and exploitation intention exercises conducted as part of this process have directly informed the selection and future promotion of core ACCTING outputs.

Publication on repositories as open access

ACCTING products, and in particular factsheets, research agendas, inspiring practices, research insights, will remain accessible post-project to ensure continued relevance and impact, and will serve as resources for advocacy, research, and policy development in Europe and beyond.

They have been published as open-source tools on the following platforms:

- [Zenodo, in a dedicated ACCTING Community](#),
- Horizon Results Platform
- CORDIS,
- [EU Agenda](#)
- Platforms of umbrella organisations:
 - o [EU-Citizen.Science](#)
 - o [ICLEI Just Transition website](#).
- Institutional and national-level repositories of research results:
 - o DiVA platform
 - o Gothenburg University Publications Electronic Archive (GUPEA)
- GenPORT: ACCTING's outputs
- [Futuresilience](#): ACCTING's policy briefs have been submitted for publication on the project's repository of policy instruments to enhance diverse aspects of societal resilience to future crises.

The homepage of the ACCTING website is currently being redesigned into a "toolbox" showcasing replicable initiatives from the project, thus extending its practical impact beyond the project lifetime. It will be hosted for 3 years beyond the project's lifetime.

Pilot Actions

A key exploitation feature of the ACCTING project has been the funding and implementation of ten innovative pilot projects across Europe which constitute a direct form of exploitation, as they have already begun creating impact and have planned to continue doing so.

Below is a summary of the exploitation strategies pursued by the pilot projects.

PA1 – “Dialogue and Action Against Wildfires” in Greece strongly engaged diverse stakeholders from four small villages, including public authorities and CSOs. 24 key individuals across four villages were strongly involved in the project in order to pursue the work in the long term; 29 local community members were trained in fire preparedness and -fighting. The pilot’s main output, a [Forest Fire Risk Reduction Toolkit](#) will continue to be promoted beyond the project’s lifetime: neighbouring villages have expressed an interest in using the toolkit to prepare for the next fire season. Building on the momentum created through the pilot project, a new non-profit organisation was created in February 2025: the Community-Led Development Institute – [Villages in Action](#). Rooted in the social and solidarity economy, the institute is currently involved in two new pilot initiatives in the region,

- Developing trail-based tourism as a lever for local development;
- Exploring citizen science approaches to rural heritage, using the issue of burning open-air olive pruning as a lens for environmental, cultural, and behavioural transformation.

Both projects deepen the participatory, community-led approach developed through previous efforts they had in the area and elevated through ACCTING with the aim to generate systemic impact in underrepresented rural areas.

lasting, *Figure 17: Community meeting organised within PA 1- Dialogue and action against wildfires*

PA 2, Echoversity – Participatory Biodiversity Conservation in Greece (Ecomuseum Zagori) offers a replicable and flexible participatory model rooted in biodiversity conservation and traditional knowledge. Its outputs, such as the biodiversity data produced within the citizen science activities is recorded and publicly available in an app, “EcholociApp”, supporting ongoing conservation efforts in the region. Educational resources blending culture and ecology are taken up by schools beyond the project’s lifetime.

Collaborative networks established between residents, researchers, local authorities, schools, and educational institutions provide a foundation for long-term sustainability. To support continuation and expansion, the pilot plans to leverage this initiative to apply for private and public grants at regional, national, and EU levels, related to eco-tourism.

PA 3, inclusivECs awards (Spain) aimed to recognise initiatives and practical examples of inclusion of vulnerable groups in energy communities in Spain. Through a 2-day forum, over 200 volunteers in energy communities were empowered to use these communities to advance social justice. Six energy community were awarded with prizes that will have a direct impact on energy efficiency improvement.

The continuous dissemination of the policy brief aims to secure funding for a new round of InclusivECs awards in 2025.

PA 4, Supporting Roma Micro-Entrepreneurs in Albania (IRCA)

This pilot focuses on long-term impact through replication and community-driven growth. The initiative combined entrepreneurship training, peer support, and resource provision to strengthen green micro-enterprises. A key exploitation pathway lies in the informal coalition and digital platform established, which will continue as a permanent support structure. IRCA plans to lobby for the integration of the programme into local strategies, working closely with authorities and donors to secure their support. Additionally, IRCA aims to expand the initiative to include other marginalized groups by scaling up its training efforts in digital and financial literacy. The development of adaptable training materials, focusing on promoting measures to increase environmental sustainability in businesses, further enhances the project's scalability. These materials allow for replication and capacity building at the local level, enabling other marginalized groups to benefit from similar support structures.

PA 5, Mapko – Community Gardens and Urban Agriculture in Czechia (Kokoza)

Mapko.cz, the digital platform improved during the project, remains active in the long-term. Not only will its improvements serve to enhance the use community gardens, new features such as multilingual content and tailored guidance, will allow the platform to be scaled and adapted for use across other regions. Partnerships built with NGOs and CSOs in Spain, France, Germany, Austria, Poland, and Bosnia have also built a strong foundation for regional and international collaboration. In Czechia, partnerships with CSOs and municipalities aim to secure long-term land access and advocate for supportive policy frameworks. Educational outreach and documentation of successful models aim to facilitate wider uptake and embed community gardens into urban planning.

PA 6, Food4Schools project (Greece) aimed at creating the framework and procedures needed for the implementation of the Farm to Fork strategy at a local level and specifically in schools of the wider area of Thessaloniki and Central Macedonia. Its resources developed (toolkit, action plan, research report) remain accessible and continuously promoted. The project will continue with some funding from EIT NEB CONNECT and attempts are in-the-making to crowdsource enough to conduct a more thorough educational project structured around the F4S toolkit, working with teachers on implementation in schools.

PA 7, EduMove – Boosting Bike Use in Suburban Tirana (Active Mobility Albania)

EduMove's exploitation strategy centres on replicability and integration into policy. The model, comprising cycling education, access to bicycles, and basic infrastructure, can be adapted for suburban or peri-urban areas lacking mobility options. The project has engaged over 500 students, installed infrastructure, and opened dialogue with national authorities to develop a national cycling curriculum. Discussions are underway with additional partners, including the Agricultural University of Tirana, to apply the model in new contexts. EduMove is also a candidate for upscaling through the ScienceUs EU-funded initiative.

PA 8, Todas en Bici (Aqui, Spain) aimed to expand the reach and impact of cycling in Barcelona, making it more accessible and inclusive. Its collective decision-making model, applied to the creation of a space for a collective governance of cycling in Barcelona with a diverse array of entities, grassroots movements and activists, was promoted within the Cycling and Society Symposium 2024, and with other cities and municipalities. Aqui intends to carry on exploiting this local success with

other regions. At the local level, the community created has been sustained by Aqvi beyond the time of the project.

PA 9, Uključi se! /Get involved! (Young Researchers of Serbia) developed a digital platform to connect projects and local actions with NGOs, CSOs, private companies and individuals, to support ideas motivating others to get involved and continue working on sustainable development and climate change. By onboarding private companies as potential funders through Corporate Social Responsibility, the project aims to secure funding to further develop the platform.

PA 10, School goes green (Per Estempio Onlus) aimed to promote the active engagement and participation of young people in the local territory, learning by practicing a healthy, equal and sustainable lifestyle. Their core resource, a [Green step-by-step guide](#) (Italian and English versions), aims to be taken up by school community representatives and civil society organisations to create similar volunteering learning experiences. Their engagement of a broad community throughout the project (including volunteers, teachers, students, local organisations, school representatives) should facilitate the replication of the initiative.

On **30 April**, a workshop was hosted in Brussels by **ICLEI** to support pilot actions in sustaining and upscaling their initiatives beyond the project's lifetime. Six of the projects who attended benefited from mutual learning and input from experts in similar fields.

These exploitation pathways ensure that the ACCTING pilot projects will generate lasting impact. Through replication, policy integration, and long-term partnerships, they offer models for inclusive and sustainable practices that can be adopted across diverse European contexts. More information about the results of the pilots and the exploitation pathways of other projects can be found in [D5.7: Pilot Actions implementation report](#).

The pilot methodology has proved to produce practical results that can be continued, replicated or scaled up, as presented in D5.7. Many pilots have developed resources such as platforms, toolkits or training models that live on beyond the project. Others created partnerships with local authorities, paving the way for their approaches to be adopted into policy or planning. Pilots are a valuable tool for policymakers seeking to support (environmental) transitions. They offer a cost-effective model by leveraging existing civil society organisations that are locally embedded, trusted, and equipped with contextual knowledge.

The learnings from the pilot methodology have also been showcased through three blog posts and promoted on social media.

- <https://accting.eu/acctings-pilots-successes/>
- <https://accting.eu/challenges-accting-pilots/>
- <https://accting.eu/lessons-learnt-acctings-pilots/>

They have also been exploited as a success story submitted to the Green Deal Support Office success story, for exploitation by other related initiatives and projects. ACCTING's final policy brief

“Aligning grassroots initiatives and institutional support for a just and inclusive Green Deal” D7.9 also features learnings from the pilots.

The results achieved by the pilots were spotlighted through all projects’ dissemination channels, including through participation in conferences, as detailed above. Four short videos promoting the projects were also produced by ACCTING in the last month of the project, recorded on the occasion of the final conference. Representatives were asked about their most memorable part of the project, and asked to share about the participatory process. The videos are available on the project’s YouTube channel in a [playlist dedicated to Pilot projects](#).

ACCTING Pilot projects ▶ Play all

Figure 18: Overview of the videos promoting pilot projects.

Other pilot representatives provided contents for an interview in a written format, published on the project website.

ACCTING Network

The ACCTING Network, one of the three dissemination pillars, is instrumental for ensuring the project’s legacy. By actively involving stakeholders throughout the project, in communication activities, in co-designing the policy guidelines (T5.1) or in the pilot actions (T5.2), the ACCTING Network was expanded with the aim to be sustained after the project lifetime.

- **Stakeholders involved in the project**, whether experts invited to the Open Studios, the webinars, final conference, or identified stakeholders from research, civil society, public authorities, and business sectors were engaged to take up the project’s fact sheets, research agendas and insights beyond the project’s lifetime. In several cases, outreach efforts have laid the groundwork for potential follow-up actions or collaborations (e.g. with policymakers, civil society, researchers, etc.). Examples include conversations around safer public transport, healthy food in schools and workplaces, gender-inclusive mobility, and forest fire prevention in rural areas.
- **Newsletters subscribers and social media followers** are invited in a final newsletter issue to join communities of sister projects, including Shared Green Deal and new projects funded under HORIZON-CL2-2023-TRANSFORMATIONS-01-10 Tackling inequalities in the green and digital transitions (ST4TE, FITTER-EU, READJUST).
- Following the success of the Pilot Action workshop organised on 30 April, **Pilot project representatives** have expressed an interest to meet on an annual basis for mutual learning and exchange.

- The [ACCTING Zenodo Community](#) will remain available and updated after the project's lifetime as a living repository of research outputs, research agendas, and recommendations related to the advancement of a just and inclusive green transition.

Further research

As a Research and Innovation Action (RIA), new knowledge was generated and promoted towards other researchers to build upon it and contribute to filling in identified knowledge gaps related to the influence of Green Deal measures on increasing or decreasing inequalities on the behaviour of people and on their impact on the economy, society and the environment.

- The two sets of **Agendas for Future Research** highlight key research gaps across Green Deal policy areas and provides a comprehensive overview of priorities for a fair and sustainable transition. These agendas have been published as standalone documents, made accessible via the ACCTING website, Zenodo community, and the EU Agenda profile of ESF. They have been complemented by a series of webinars aimed at engaging stakeholders, fostering uptake, and stimulating future research projects. Their target audiences include research funders, policymakers, and the wider scientific community, particularly in the domains of Green Deal and social justice.
- **25 scientific articles and book chapters** have been submitted for publication to this date. 8 draft articles are at an advanced stage and currently under internal peer-review for submission after the project's termination. Partners also have other plans to write papers based on ACCTING's research in further publications beyond the project lifetime.
- **The paper already published (Boostani 2024) has to this date been cited in 4 papers:**
 - Arias, A.; Husiev, O.; Schwaller, C.; Sturm, U. Terminologies and concepts of energy cooperations in Europe: A systematic review of characteristics, potentials, and challenges. *Energy Research & Social Science* **2025**, 122, 104012 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2025.104012>.
 - Kamin, T., Golob, U., & Kogovšek, T. (2025). Barriers to the Diffusion of Clean Energy Communities: Comparing Early Adopters and the General Public. *Energies*, 18(9), 2248. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en18092248>
 - Muftić Dedović, M., Avdaković, S., Mujezinović, A., Dautbašić, N., Alihodžić, A., & Memić, A. (2025). Energy Poverty in Bosnia and Herzegovina: Challenges, Solutions, and Policy Recommendations. *Energies*, 18(1), 43. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en18010043>
 - Monica Laura Zlati & Angelica Buboï (Danaila) & Costinela Fortea & Alina Meca & Valentin Marian Antohi, 2024. "[Studying Regional Disparities at European Level with a View to Achieving Climate Neutrality Objectives](#)," [Economics and Applied Informatics](#), "Dunarea de Jos" University of Galati, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, issue 3, pages 361-373.
- **Partners' research and teaching**

The research teams in the consortium will use the ACCTING research results in their own or shared future work, including teaching.

- **Ongoing and future research projects**

- [ST4TE](#): ACCTINGs theoretical and methodological framework is applied in ST4TE where they use narrative and intersectional analysis to understand impact of the green, digital and twin transition on inequalities.
- PHOENIX Horizon expressed interest in taking up ACCTING’s intersectional framework in their research.

Research outputs have relevance for the new calls of the work programmes within Horizon Europe and will be exploited by partners applying for these calls.

- **Surveys**

The dataset of ACCTING’s narratives has been submitted to the [European Social Survey](#) for potential uptake. The European Social Survey (ESS) provides high-quality open access data measuring public attitudes, beliefs and behaviour.

Policy-making

The ACCTING project has significantly contributed to policy-making processes by developing actionable and context-sensitive recommendations aimed at reducing inequalities in the implementation of the European Green Deal. A central pathway for this policy influence has been the dissemination of the thirteen thematic factsheets, used to initiate dialogue and co-creation processes across multiple governance levels.

As described above, ACCTING partners engaged in direct conversations with local, regional and national authorities, using the factsheets to introduce evidence-based approaches in areas such as safer public transport, inclusive food systems, sustainable mobility and disaster preparedness. Examples include policy dialogues with the City of Lisbon, the Municipality of İzmir, and regional agrotech clusters in Thessaloniki; the involvement of stakeholders from the transport sector during the Belgian seminar “Veilig Onderweg”; and collaboration with municipalities and academic institutions in Romania, Portugal, Sweden and Turkey.

Policy uptake was also supported through high-visibility contributions to events such as the EU Green Week, the European Urban Resilience Forum, and national roundtables. Furthermore, the ACCTING advocacy webinars served as policy fora in themselves, enabling interaction between researchers, civil society and policymakers on inclusive climate governance, safety, sustainable food systems, and community-based resilience.

In some cases, the project’s recommendations were integrated into ongoing local strategies (e.g. on food procurement in Thessaloniki, or disaster risk preparedness in Greece), while in others, they inspired further dialogue and opened avenues for future collaboration. In Belgium, the “Towards Safer Mobility” factsheet catalysed national-level discussions on violence in public transport, bringing together operators and safety experts to explore policy interventions. In Portugal, the food access factsheet prompted renewed dialogue with the municipalities of Lisbon and Cascais, including plans

for further engagement via dedicated sessions in Portuguese. In Romania, the recommendations on sustainable food and inclusive workplace practices opened conversations with local authorities and chambers of commerce. Similarly, in Sweden, ACCTING's outputs on food and health have been channelled into planned magazine articles and stakeholder seminars aiming to influence municipal governance. In Turkey, the translation and adaptation of selected factsheets led to their use in meetings with newly elected municipal administrations. The factsheets, webinars and pilot actions collectively acted as vehicles for operationalising the project's research into policy conversations, enabling partners to contextualise findings, build trust, and create openings for inclusive policy co-design to take place beyond the project's lifetime.

Although structural policy change requires longer-term processes, ACCTING has laid a strong foundation by fostering knowledge co-production, relational engagement, and cross-sectoral alliances. These pathways demonstrate how research-based recommendations can meaningfully inform inclusive and just policymaking under the Green Deal. While formal policy uptake may take time to materialise, ACCTING's advocacy activities have already opened several potential pathways for exploitation in the policy-making sphere.

Conclusion

Over the 40-month duration of the ACCTING project, substantial efforts were invested in disseminating knowledge, engaging diverse stakeholders, and advocating for inclusive policies under the European Green Deal. These activities have not only ensured visibility for ACCTING's outputs but have also laid the groundwork for their continued relevance and uptake beyond the formal project period.

The project's extensive outreach, through awareness-raising, scientific publications, participation in conferences, organisation of webinars, pilot actions, community engagement, and advocacy, has initiated a strong momentum for behavioural and structural change. However, meaningful transformation, particularly in addressing entrenched inequalities and fostering inclusive sustainability, is a long-term process. Policy shifts, societal mindsets, and institutional practices evolve gradually, and the full impact of ACCTING's work will unfold over time.

ACCTING's exploitation strategy ensures that the project's outputs remain active assets for change. Research agendas and insights, factsheets, policy briefs, inspiring initiatives, and project learnings have been made openly accessible and are embedded within networks of policymakers, civil society organisations, and local actors. Many of these stakeholders have expressed intent to continue using and adapting ACCTING's insights in their respective domains, from municipal planning and advocacy to further research, educational and funding programmes.

Pilot projects, in particular, serve as proof-of-concept interventions with strong potential for replication and scaling. The alliances formed with grassroots initiatives, local authorities, and thematic networks will act as vehicles for continued dissemination and implementation. Furthermore, the curated repository of resources on platforms such as Zenodo and the project's website ensures that the knowledge generated will remain discoverable and usable by researchers and practitioners in years to come.

In summary, while ACCTING as a funded project concludes, its pathways for exploitation extend well beyond its official timeline. The seeds sown through its communication and dissemination efforts are expected to continue influencing policies, practices, and research agendas. Change takes time, but with a solid foundation in place and active engagement from its community, ACCTING's legacy will persist in shaping a fairer, more inclusive green transition.

Appendix

The following publications issued from the project have been internally peer-reviewed and made open access on the Zenodo community.

Dataset

Strid, S., Balkmar, D., Zorell, C., White, J., & Boström, M. (2024). Narratives on inequalities in enablers and hindrances for advancing behavioural change through an inclusive Green Deal in Europe. ACCTING dataset [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10522048>

Project deliverables

- Carnevale, A., Pellegrini Masini, G., Klöckner, C. A., Altınay, A. G., Düzel, E., Türeli, B. B., Kerremans, A., Denis, A., & Cacace, M. (2023). *ACCTING D2.2 - Report on inspiring practice cases* (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7711880>
- Strid, S., Balkmar, D., Zorell, C., White, J., & Boström, M. (2024). *Narratives on inequalities in enablers and hindrances for advancing behavioural change through an inclusive Green Deal in Europe. ACCTING dataset* (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10522048>
- Botha, D., & Niethammer, J. (2025). *ACCTING Deliverable 5.7: Pilot Actions implementation report*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15275659>
- Sharma, N., Cerrato, S., Zaharis, N., Celebi, D., Stergiadis, C., Denis, A., Kerremans, A., Nys, A., Zorell, C., Strid, S., Cacace, M., Duzel, E., Borhan Türeli, B., Botha, D., & Niethammer, J. (2025). *Operational Guidelines and Recommendations for an Inclusive European Green Deal – 2nd Cycle*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15058119>
- Klados, M., White, J., Zorell, C., Gajdusek, M. F., Szudi, G., Pellegrini-Masini, G., Boostani, P., Strid, S., Abrantes, P., Moreno, L., Ferreira, D., Fonseca, M. L., Vivas, A., Chatzimpyros, V., Balkmar, D., Quinti, G., & Cacace, M. (2023). *Research Agenda - 1st Cycle*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078971>
- Celebi, D., Stergiadis, C., Klados, M., & Zaharis, N. (2025). *ACCTING Research Agendas - 2nd cycle*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15534103>
- Quinti, G. M., d'Andrea, L., & Cacace, M. (2025). *ACCTING Consolidated evaluation results report*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15534375>
- Zorell, C. & Strid, S. (Eds.), (2025). *Overall report on results of the eight thematic research lines: Intersectional and qualitative comparative analyses. ACCTING Deliverable D3.4. 146 pages. Submitted to the European Commission 28 May 2025.* Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15532836>

- Zorell, C., Strid, S., & ACCTING consortium. (2023). For an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal: Integrating gendered and intersectional perspectives in Green Deal policies: Policy Brief #1. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078909>
- Denis, A., Kerremans, A., Madesi, V., Botha, D., & ACCTING Consortium. (2024). *Ensuring an Inclusive Farm to Fork Strategy: ACCTING Policy Brief #2* (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10664409>
- Schrodi, C., Zorell, C., & ACCTING consortium (2025) ACCTING D7.9. Policy Brief #3: Aligning grassroots initiatives and institutional support for a just and inclusive Green Deal. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15528337>

Factsheets

1. Nys, A., Cacace, M., & Denis, A. (2025). ACCTING Factsheet: Towards safer mobility: A holistic approach to tackling violence in public transportation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15183408>
2. Çelebi Gonidis, D., Kerremans, A., & Sharma, N. (2025). ACCTING Factsheet: Wellbeing as a trigger for behavioural change. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15005556>
3. Duzel, E., Borhan Türeli, B., Cacace, M., Strid, S., & Zorell, C. (2025). ACCTING Factsheet: Transformative resistance for a just and inclusive European Green Deal. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15006314>
4. Zorell, C., Duzel, E., & Strid, S. (2025). ACCTING Factsheet: Resisting a narrow vision of public interest. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15006056>
5. Kerremans, A., Niethammer, J., & Sharma, N. (2025). ACCTING Factsheet: Promoting policy innovations that promote commons. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15006410>
6. Zaharis, N., Botha, D., & Niethammer, J. (2025). ACCTING Factsheet: Public civil society partnerships for behavioural change. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15006455>
7. Stergiadis, C., Borhan Türeli, B., & Duzel, E. (2025). ACCTING Factsheet: Commons for all. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15006483>
8. Sharma, N., & Zorell, C. (2023). ACCTING Factsheet: Promoting access to healthy and environmentally friendly food for the marginalised and vulnerable. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8355608>
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